

Physiological and Psychological Characterisation of Young Onset

Dementia: A Case Control Study

Ethan Christopher James Berry (B00343919)

27th June 2024

**Thesis submitted in fulfilment of the requirements of the University of the West of
Scotland
for the award of Master of Research**

Word count: 11992

THIS THESIS HAS NOT BEEN SUBMITTED PREVIOUSLY FOR A COMPARABLE DEGREE

Acknowledgements

The work presented is the result of my Master of Research (MRes) thesis which took place at The University of the West of Scotland. The research and data collection for the study took place in the Sport and Physical Activity Research Institute (SPARI) at the Lanarkshire campus. The study aim was to profile young onset dementia physiologically and psychologically with the aim of identifying what deficiencies (if any) could be improved with exercise or physical activity. The completion of the study was only possible through the help of many people whom I would like to thank.

In the first instance, I would like to thank my lead supervisor Dr Lawrence Hayes, who gave me a place on this project and who employed me as a research assistant. Throughout my course, Lawrence has always been there to support and guide me through the challenges of data collection and writing up my thesis. I owe a huge amount to him for my development as a researcher. I would also like to thank my secondary supervisor Prof. Nicholas Sculthorpe; his expertise and guidance has helped me develop my research skills and learn methodological skills. I would like to thank Dr Marie McLaughlin for her guidance during complex analysis, without this support I would have struggled to analyse a large portion of my results. The guidance of Dr Nilihan Sanal-Hayes was invaluable in my understanding of the psychological aspects of the study to whom I am thankful. I am grateful to the lab technicians for always allowing me adequate space and equipment to carry out the data collection, this piece of research would not have been possible without you.

A special thanks should go to the NHS Lanarkshire team for helping us with the identification and recruitment of participants, as well as the participants themselves for giving up their time to contribute within the lab and during the remote segments of the study. Further thanks should go to the control group for their enthusiasm for taking part.

Finally, I would like to thank my partner, family, and friends for their undying support. Their commitment to believing in me has pushed me to work to my maximum to do them proud. They have helped remind me that there is more to life than working, this has allowed me to step back and reassess when times get tough. Without their love and support this thesis would simply not have been possible.

Table of Contents

1. List of Figures	1
2. List of Tables	2
3. Abstract	3
4. Introduction	5
5. Methods	16
6. Results	26
7. Discussion	37
8. References	45
9. Appendices	68

1. List of Figures

- 1 **Figure 1.** Estimated $\dot{V}O_{2\max}$ data from people with young onset dementia (YOD; n = 16) and controls (n = 17) from a submaximal Astrand-Rhyming test. Data are presented as individual dot plots with accompanying mean line.
- 2 **Figure 2.** Vascular function parameters from people with young onset dementia (YOD; n = 16) and controls (n = 17). Data are presented as individual dot plots with accompanying mean line.
- 3 **Figure 3.** Muscle architecture parameters from people with young onset dementia (YOD; n = 16) and controls (n = 17). Data are presented as individual dot plots with accompanying mean line (fascicle length, pennation angle and USI) and median line (muscle thickness).
- 4 **Figure 4.** Peak flow data from people with young onset dementia (YOD; n = 16) and controls (n = 17). Data are presented as individual dot plots with accompanying mean line.
- 5 **Figure 5.** Handgrip strength data from people with young onset dementia (YOD; n = 16) and controls (n = 17). Data are presented as individual dot plots with accompanying mean line.
- 6 **Figure 6.** Physical activity parameters from people with young onset dementia (YOD; n = 16) and controls (n = 17). Data are presented as individual dot plots with accompanying mean line (LPA and MVPA) and median line (sedentary time).
- 7 **Figure 7.** Dexterity and fine motor skills parameters from the Purdue Pegboard Test in people with young onset dementia (YOD; n = 16) and controls (n = 17). Data are presented as individual dot plots with accompanying mean line (both hands, left + right + both hands and assembly) and median line (left hand and right hand).
- 8 **Figure 8.** Cognitive function parameters from people with young onset dementia (YOD; n = 16) and controls (n = 17). Data are presented as individual dot plots with accompanying median line.
- 9 **Figure 9.** GAD-7 data from people with young onset dementia (YOD; n = 16) and controls (n = 17). Data are presented as individual dot plots with accompanying median line.
- 10 **Figure 10.** PHQ-9 data from people with young onset dementia (YOD; n = 16) and controls (n = 17). Data are presented as individual dot plots with accompanying median line.
- 11 **Figure 11.** EQ-5D-3L parameters from people with young onset dementia (YOD; n = 16) and controls (n = 17). Data are presented as individual dot plots with accompanying mean line.

12 Figure 12. GSE data from people with young onset dementia (YOD; n = 16) and controls (n = 17). Data are presented as individual dot plots with accompanying median line.

13 Figure 13. Global PSQI data from people with young onset dementia (YOD; n = 16) and controls (n = 17). Data are presented as individual dot plots with accompanying median line.

2. List of Tables

1. Table 1: Descriptive data of participants at enrolment.

3. Abstract

Purpose: Young Onset Dementia (YOD) makes up around 5% of dementia cases and is linked to various aetiologies and risk factors. Exercise is proposed to improve fitness and reduce cognitive decline, but targeted interventions require understanding which physiological systems benefit.

Aim: To compare physiological and psychological outcomes between YOD individuals and age/sex-matched controls. It was hypothesised people with YOD would score lesser across all parameters.

Methods: This study assessed body composition, blood pressure, dexterity, cognitive function, vascular function, muscle architecture, lung function, estimated maximal oxygen uptake ($\dot{V}O_{2max}$), functional capacity, physical activity, and mental wellbeing in YOD individuals (n=16) compared to controls (n=17).

Results: YOD individuals showed significantly poorer outcomes in dexterity (left $p = 0.013$, $d = 1.0$; large effect, right $p = 0.008$, $d = 1.0$; large effect, both $p < 0.001$, $d = 1.40$; large effect, Left + right + both $p < 0.001$, $d = 1.30$; large effect, assembly $p < 0.001$, $d = 1.60$; large effect), cognitive function ($p < 0.001$, $d = 3.60$; large effect), muscle architecture (fascicle length: $p=0.028$, $d=0.81$; large effect), physical activity (Sedentary Time: $p = 0.029$, $d = 0.54$; moderate effect, Moderate-Vigorous Physical Activity (MVPA): $p = 0.014$, $d=0.97$; large effect), and mental wellbeing (Self Assessed Health Related Quality of Life - EQ-5D-3L analog score: $p=0.007$, $d=1.10$; large effect; General Self Efficacy Scale - GSE: $p<0.001$, $d=1.29$; large effect). No differences were found in estimated $\dot{V}O_{2max}$, vascular function, muscle architecture (thickness, pennation angle and USI), lung function, functional capacity, and some mental wellbeing measures (Generalised Anxiety Disorder Assessment - GAD-7, Patient Health Questionnaire - PHQ-9, EQ-5D-3L index score, Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index - PSQI).

Conclusions: The study highlights significant physical, cognitive, and psychological differences in YOD individuals, underscoring the need for tailored, multicomponent exercise interventions. These

findings support future research to develop specific protocols to improve outcomes for YOD individuals, which should target dexterity, muscle architecture, estimated $\dot{V}O_{2max}$, and mental wellbeing.

4. Introduction

Definitions, Incidence and Symptomology

Dementia is a neurodegenerative condition which leads to partial or complete loss of cognitive function (Aarsland, 2020). It is best described as a syndrome rather than one singular disease type (Rodgers et al., 2018). There are a host of risk factors associated with dementia such as age, level of education, diet, alcohol use, sleep, smoking and a range of other factors including chronic comorbidities (Anstey et al., 2019). Between 1990 and 2016 the number of people impacted by dementia increased by 117% as cases increased globally (Nichols et al., 2022). In 2015, the number of people suffering from dementia was 50 million worldwide (Handley, Bunn, and Goodman, 2017) and Nichols et al. (2022) predicted this would rise to 152 million by 2050 because of the global ageing population. People are now living long enough to experience dementia and therefore the more people age, the more develop dementia and the cycle continues (Langa, 2018). Lower income countries have faced the brunt of this increased incidence however, countries in North America and Europe have seen a reduction in incidence of up to 13% per decade since 1988 (Wolters et al., 2020) attributed to their decades' long wealth advantage (Roehr et al., 2018). The global cost of dementia is expected to increase to between \$1.6-2.4 trillion in 2050 (Pedroza et al., 2019). Alzheimer's disease (AD) is currently the leading cause of dementia worldwide, it is attributed to 60% of worldwide dementia cases (Rizzi, Rosses and Roriz-Cruz 2014) and affects approximately 10% of all persons aged over 65 years of age (Mosconi, 2013). Another common type of dementia is vascular dementia, a collection of diseases which is responsible for up to 25% of worldwide cases (O'Brien and Thomas, 2015). Frontotemporal dementia (FTD) is the third most common dementia (MacKenzie and Neumann, 2016), and makes up 10-20% of dementia cases and affects 250,000 people in the USA (Onyike and Diehl-Schmid, 2014). Other forms of dementia include Lewy Body dementia, alcohol related dementia, Parkinson's disease dementia and mixed dementia which are less common, but just as damaging (Duong, Patel, and Chang, 2017).

Young Onset Dementia (YOD) is the onset of dementia symptoms before the age of 65 (Hendriks et al., 2021), and makes up 5% of all dementia cases in the UK and up to 3.9 million cases worldwide

(Rodgers et al., 2018). In a systematic review Hendriks et al. (2022) highlighted an average time of 4.4 years between symptom onset and diagnosis of YOD. YOD tends to be more varied in symptomology compared to late onset dementia, and early symptoms include behaviour change and difficulties in language (Hendriks et al., 2021). The average life expectancy of the condition is 7.9 years from diagnosis, emphasising the aggressiveness of the condition (Brodaty, Seeher and Gibson, 2012). With specific regards to prevalence of dementia subtypes, Panegyres and Frencham (2007) found of 112 people with YOD 19% presented with FTD compared to under 12% presenting with AD. However, a study by Harvey, Skelton-Robinson and Rossor (2003) found of 185 participants only 12% were comprised of FTD and 34% had AD, although this study excluded those with brain injuries which may have underrepresented FTD (Kelley et al., 2008). Hendriks et al. (2022) found AD to be the most common type of dementia in people aged 45-65. However, since the development of further clinical recognition of FTD (Neary et al., 1998) the number diagnosed with FTD YOD has increased (Sampson, Warren and Rossor, 2004). It is clear in much of the literature that although AD is dominant in YOD, diagnoses tend to be more varied compared to LOD (Rossor et al., 2010).

Differences Between YOD and LOD

There are multiple differences between YOD and LOD incidence. The Hendriks et al. (2022) systematic review found global incidence of YOD was 11 per 100,000 people aged 30-64, using the 2019 global population this equates to 370,000 new YOD cases annually. At present, the annual incidence of LOD is around 4 per 1,000 people aged 65-69 years, increasing to 65 per 1,000 people aged 85-89 years (Wolters et al., 2020). People with YOD are more likely to be working than people with LOD (Wong et al., 2020), which has a unique impact upon the person and their family, as they may have to cease working at diagnosis (Kilty et al., 2022). Up to 60% of those with YOD present with aggressive behaviour (Hewitt et al., 2013), which is 20% more than in LOD (Kolanowski and Garr, 1999), which have adverse effects on those with YOD's ability to work. Those with YOD are more likely to suffer from compulsive behaviours than those with LOD, which may also impact on their employability (O'Malley et al., 2021).

There are differences in symptoms between the two conditions, for example, YOD AD causes more apraxia and executive dysfunction than in LOD as it predominately impairs attentional skills (Koedam et al., 2010). Psychologically, Wong et al. (2020) reported 33% of those with YOD had a previous diagnosis of depression compared to 25% in LOD. This is mirrored in Koopmans and Rosness (2014) who found out of 196 people with YOD 36% used antidepressant drugs. Depression does not appear to be the only psychological problem in YOD, as Novek, Shooshtari and Menec (2016) found nearly half (49%) of the YOD group in their study had a previously diagnosed psychiatric disorder. These psychological issues may be attributed, in part, to the sense of apathy which accompanies YOD diagnosis (Draper and Withhall, 2016).

The previous paragraphs have focussed on the differences between YOD and LOD incidence and symptoms. In addition to these observed differences, Wong et al. (2020) found stark health-related disparities, with 30% of people with YOD exhibiting heart disease compared to 38% in the LOD sample. This may be attributed to age and coinciding increased risk of heart disease (Rodgers et al., 2019). Physical activity and fitness levels are higher in those with YOD (Rodgers et al., 2018), but observations of lower physical activity in LOD may be an artefact of their advanced age, and longitudinal studies are required to separate the effect of age and dementia type (YOD or LOD). Parry et al. (2018) found residents in a care home with LOD spent 85% of the day sedentary. Despite people with YOD being generally more physically active than people with LOD (Beattie et al., 2004), the early age at which YOD symptoms occur may start a cascade of physical and mental decline at a faster rate than LOD (Tolhurst et al., 2012). This cascade induces habits of sedentary behaviour disproportionate to their age (Rodgers et al., 2018). Therefore, comparing YOD and LOD for physical activity levels is less insightful than comparing YOD and age-matched controls, which would provide information as to whether people with YOD are more inactive than their age-matched peers.

Aetiology and Risk Factors in YOD

There are many aetiologies involved in YOD which differ based on the type of dementia. One cause of YOD is AD, which begins manifesting in the entorhinal cortex and progresses to the hippocampus (Owens et al., 2021; Owens et al., 2022). As hippocampal neurons degenerate, memory begins to falter and further spreading of the disease causes language to be affected (Rimmer and Smith, 2009). This process starts with mutations in gamma and beta-secretases that breakdown amyloid precursor protein (APP) into an insoluble fragment that causes build-up of beta amyloid proteins and tau protein (Moussa, 2017). This occurs in the extracellular space between neurons building up plaques and neurofibrillary tangles leading to neuronal death and hippocampal atrophy (Hölscher, 1998). YOD AD cases tend to be familial, meaning they have an inherited gene mutation in PSEN-1 or PSEN-2 (Siddappaji and Gopal, 2021). There has been some scrutiny regarding the beta amyloid cascade hypothesis within the literature. For example, Morris, Clark and Vissel (2014) stated despite increased beta amyloid expression in those with Down Syndrome, not all develop AD, suggesting it is not the sole risk factor for AD.

Vascular dementia is caused by cerebral hypoxia, damaging the white matter of the sub-cortex (Ladecola, 2014). It is often a direct result of cerebrovascular disease, a group of conditions affecting cerebral vasculature (Lee, 2011). In YOD, vascular dementia manifests through several aetiologies (Masellis et al., 2013), with many cases associated with vascular risk factors such as high blood pressure (BP) and hyperlipidaemia (Rossor et al., 2010). High prevalence of sedentary behaviours in YOD make vascular dementia a primary cause for concern (Knopman et al., 2001) as sedentary behaviours increase stroke risk by 21% (Wang et al., 2022), stroke causes a breakdown in cerebral blood flow leading to neuronal breakdown (Denkinger et al., 2011). Due to exercises protective effects on the cerebral vasculature (Hillman, Snook, and Jerome, 2003; Barnes and Corkery, 2018), it is possible a large portion of YOD vascular dementia could be prevented.

In younger demographics, FTD is more common (Harvey, Skelton-Robinson and Rossor 2003), comprising three main subtypes; behavioural variant, semantic dementia, and non-fluent aphasia (Rossor et al., 2010). Genetics is 40% predictive of FTD and Chow et al. (1999) reported the average age of onset for familial cases was 56 years. The behavioural variant of the condition is the most

heritable (Rohrer et al., 2009), this variant is associated with changes in personality and behaviour (Chow et al., 1999). Many YOD cases have gene mutations in microtubule associated protein tau (Rohrer and Warren, 2011) which leads to aggregation (Weder et al., 2007) and the associated tangles act as a physical barrier to neuronal pathways, causing neuronal loss (Mohandas, Rajmohan, and Raghunath, 2009). This dementia causes long-term atrophy of the frontal and temporal lobes mainly affecting speech, language, personality, and behaviour (Seelaar et al., 2010).

The previous paragraphs have highlighted the neurodegenerative pathologies associated with YOD. However, there are other risk factors relating to endothelial dysfunction (Trigiani and Hamel, 2017). Heath, Mercer, and Guthrie (2015) found that a diabetes diagnosis was associated with a 2x increased risk of YOD as hyperglycaemia can damage cerebral vasculature (Seaquist, 2010). Nordstrom et al. (2013) linked increased alcohol consumption with a 5x increased risk of all types of YOD, alcohol abuse causes a 30% downregulation in glucose metabolism in the temporal and thalamic regions causing neurodegeneration (Gibson et al., 2016). Interestingly, when physical activity is statistically adjusted for studies have shown development of the discussed risk factors decrease by 30% (Cho et al., 2020), suggesting physical activity is imperative to reduce risk of YOD. In addition to vascular risk factors, traumatic brain injury (TBI) has been reported by Graham and Sharp (2019) to have a strong association with AD. A meta-analysis by Li et al., (2017) on 2 million people with TBI showed a 1.6x greater risk of YOD. Brain injuries cause neuron death due to axonal shear lesions that occur when force is exerted on the brain (McKee and Daneshvar, 2015) which can upregulate the deposition of amyloid (Seeley et al., 2009). Field et al. (2003) showed TBI (concussion) to be more damaging for younger populations than older populations, due to developing brains having more vulnerability in the hippocampal regions.

Exercise and Dementia

Exercise has repeatedly been shown to be preventative for dementia, and to slow disease progression (Trigiani and Hamel, 2017; Ahlskog et al., 2011). However, no exercise study to date has 'cured' dementia and we do not propose this is possible. There are several mechanisms that exercise exerts, which may slow dementia progression (Gholamnezhad, Boskabady and Jahangiri, 2020). Erickson et

al. (2011) used magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) which is a type of scan that uses strong magnetic fields and radio waves to produce detailed images of inside the body alongside spatial memory tests to image brains of 165 adults (67 ± 5.6) after one year of aerobic and stretching exercise three times per week. They found the exercise group had greater hippocampal volume and memory scores compared to controls. However, the adults in this study were those without dementia diagnosis and it is invalid to expect these positive effects in YOD or LOD due to hippocampal degeneration disproportionate to the normal ageing brain in these conditions (Van De Pol et al., 2006).

Exercise increases brain derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF) (Sleiman et al., 2016). Damirchi et al. (2017) found aerobic and combined aerobic and cognitive training at 55-75% heart rate (HR) maximum 3 days per week increased serum BDNF levels in 24 women with cognitive impairment. The results of this study also showed increased working memory in the cognitive training and exercise training groups compared to controls post intervention. However, this study had a small sample and the lack of studies applying this design in people with YOD or LOD means it is unclear whether this stimulus is enough to elicit positive BDNF changes. Further to this point, many similar studies show that this mechanism happens, but not that it is effective. It is possible BDNF may increase in serum, but it is unclear if it always binds with Tropomyosin receptor kinase B (TrkB) in the brain and if this binding causes enough downstream gene expression to cause an effect we can detect. Overall, meaning it is unclear if this mechanism is beneficial in YOD or LOD. Carotid blood flow has been shown to be improved by exercise, the study by Sato et al. (2011) highlighted in 10 healthy adults during an incremental cycle ergometer $\dot{V}O_2$ measurement that carotid blood flow increased to 500 ml/min when working at 80% $\dot{V}O_{2max}$. It is key to note carotid artery stiffness is increased in those with dementia (Hughes et al., 2018) and so increased carotid blood flow may not reach the same potential.

Despite positive findings, understanding of the mechanistic underpinning for exercise benefitting cognition in dementia is lacking. For example, Yu et al. (2021) utilised a 12-month exercise intervention with 96 AD participants and found decline in the AD cognitive scale score was stabilised in all exercise groups. However, no neuroimaging techniques were used in the study and so the mechanisms of the improvement are unclear. In this context, Nanda, Balde and Manjunatha (2013) utilised a single group

aerobic intervention involving 1 bout of 30 minutes exercise with 10 healthy adults and observed improved cognitive tests. It is possible these findings are coincidental as improvement in the tests may be from memory rather than any mechanistic exercise effects. It is unclear specifically in YOD due to the aggressive nature of onset which (if any) physiological pathways may be improved by exercise and how this effects cognition (Metteling et al. (2021).

Exercise has been shown to reduce cerebral beta amyloid accumulation in animals (Tan et al., 2021). For example, the study by Thomas et al. (2020) used 15-month-old mice in a treadmill exercise intervention, where the animals ran at 15m/min and 32m/min during a 15-month intervention. They found there was reduced amyloid plaque burden in the hippocampus compared to controls. The use of rodents is common as they can be euthanised and neurological changes to their brain examined in autopsy (Stillman et al., 2016). It is difficult to compare rodent findings in amyloid reduction to that of human studies as accumulating amyloid in the brains of rodents is physically and chemically different to human brains (Kokjohn and Roher, 2009). The study by Jensen et al. (2016) used a 16-week aerobic program on 53 human participants with AD, baseline cerebral spinal fluid (CSF) and post intervention CSF were analysed to assess amyloid. The results highlighted no change to the level of amyloid for any of the participants. Further studies by Vidoni et al. (2021) measured amyloid via positron emission tomography (PET) before and after an aerobic exercise intervention in older adults with and without elevated amyloid. There was no change in amyloid burden found suggesting the positive amyloid reduction findings in humans are trivial.

The most studied form of exercise training for people living with dementia is aerobic exercise due to its wide availability and ease of access (Ahlskog et al., 2011). The World Health Organisation (WHO) has recommended aerobic physical activity as a suitable intervention for preventing dementia (Groot et al., 2016). Rimmer and Smith (2009, pp. 368-374) stated that current literature around aerobic exercise have shown positive effects in those with AD through gains in physical fitness, slower decline in mental status not typical of AD and significant improvement in cognitive measures. However, the improved measures are not specified leaving it unclear what components can be improved by exercise. Sobol et al. (2016) found that moderate-vigorous aerobic exercise three times per week for 16 weeks improved

cardiorespiratory fitness in AD subjects. However, the sample were elderly and likely led a sedentary lifestyle (Hartman et al., 2018) and so scope for cardiorespiratory improvement is increased regardless of dementia. Salisbury, Mathiason and Yu (2022) found a 6-month cycling intervention seen a group of elderly adults with mild Alzheimer's disease increase their $\dot{V}O_{2max}$ by $1.28 \text{ mL}\cdot\text{kg}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ this is a clinically significant finding as $\dot{V}O_{2max}$ values in these groups are below average attributed to their condition (Plini et al., 2023). Despite these positive findings, there is a lack of evidence for exercise increasing fitness in YOD and it is unclear what is the optimal dosage.

As discussed, aerobic exercise has been found to improve physical fitness in some studies of dementia (Wang et al., 2021; Graff-Radford, 2011). However, it also has potential to improve cognitive function. Cancela et al. (2016) in an RCT with 114 AD subjects, found a 15 minute per day aerobic cycling program improved mini mental state examination (MMSE) scores from baseline in an exercise group compared to controls. However, this program was carried out on individuals who were institutionalised and may not be applicable to community-dwelling adults. Vreugdenhill et al. (2012) found a 4-month aerobic walking program for 40 people with AD who had a mean age of 74 improved MMSE scores from baseline. However, it is important to note that this program was completed in a social environment, and it is unclear whether these interactions improved cognitive function, or it was solely an exercise effect. It should be noted that benefits may depend on the degree of neuronal loss (Law et al., 2020) and so due to the aggressive onset of YOD it is unclear whether any benefits can be observed. Aerobic exercise has also been demonstrated to improve quality of life (QOL) in dementia, Yang et al. (2015) highlighted in people with AD an aerobic cycling training intervention at 70% of maximum HR for 3 months improved QOL score. However, as with much of the literature there is a lack of findings regarding exercise and improved QOL in YOD, this is poignant as improved QOL in LOD will be highly different to improved QOL in YOD due to age differences (Rodgers et al., 2018).

As discussed, people with dementia present with various comorbidities, either increasing risk of dementia, or dementia increasing the risk of comorbidities. Despite much of the existent research on exercise in dementia considering aerobic exercise types, Dost et al. (2022) reported that of 166 people with AD, 53% presented with sarcopenia, highlighting the multi-systems effect of ageing. Cadore et al.

(2014) attempted to combat this multimorbidity with a resistance-based training approach aimed at improving muscular strength. This involved 18 people with dementia and consisted of four weeks of cognitive and balance training followed by four weeks of resistance training. Strength was improved post intervention however, the absence of a control group meant improvements can't be quantified relative to no intervention. Further studies by Borba-Pinhheiro et al. (2013) used a program on one subject living with FTD consisting of 4 months of resistance training at 65-90% of 10RM. Lower limb strength was improved for the subject. Despite this evidence, there is a distinct lack of studies directly quantifying resistance-based strength gains in YOD, it is possible those with YOD may need more intense programs to observe strength gain (Keller and Engelhardt, 2013).

Like aerobic exercise, resistance exercise has been put forward as a means of improving cognitive function (Coelho-Junior et al., 2022). The study by Vital et al. (2012) used the clock drawing test and verbal fluency test to assess cognition alongside a resistance training program. They concluded resistance training to have no improvement on cognitive function in 34 elderly people with AD. This study utilised low intensity resistance training which may not have been an optimal stimulus to affect cognition. In this context Hong, Kim, and Jun (2018) compared 22 subjects in a resistance training group completing 15R of 60% 1RM for 12 weeks to a control group and found cognitive decline was attenuated as neuropsychological test scores remained unchanged. There are key issues in parts of the research linking resistance training to slowing cognitive decline or improving it for example, Holthoff et al. (2015) demonstrated a 3-month lower limb resistance program was linked to improved executive and language ability in 30 subjects with AD relative to controls. However, using a similar design Toots et al. (2017) highlighted that a 4-month lower limb program with 186 subjects with various types of dementia resulted in no improvements in MMSE score. The first study's participants had a mean age of 72 and the latter was 85, the heterogenous sample sizes across studies has resulted in differing findings and an unclear consensus for what is optimal to improve or slow cognitive decline in dementia relative to their age and stage of disease. However, much of the research does not directly measure cognitive function alongside resistance training in those with YOD therefore, it is unclear the potential resistance training has for improving cognitive function or slowing disease progression.

The previous discussions have considered aerobic training and resistance training respectively however, it is not always the case that these are conducted in isolation. With regards to the ‘combined training’ approach Bossers et al. (2015) concluded that scores in tests of global cognition, visual and verbal memory and executive function were all higher in the combined group compared with the aerobic only, balance and leg endurance also seen greater improvement in the combined group. In the RCT by Lamb et al. (2018), they used a combined aerobic and strength intervention in a group of 329 people living with AD and compared their score in the AD cognitive scale to a control group. After the 12 month follow up, AD cognitive scale score still declined in both however, it is possible a longer intervention may have seen effects. The meta-analysis by Groot et al. (2016) reported that interventions from 18 studies that included both aerobic and resistance were more beneficial (SMD = 0.59) to physical and cognitive function than aerobic only (SMD = 0.41). Overall, it is apparent different forms of exercise training can have a benefit in dementia populations (Sampaio et al., 2021) however, there is still confusion regarding what is optimal in both YOD and LOD.

YOD and Exercise Training

The current literature concerning exercise and dementia has primarily focussed on LOD. A meta-analysis by Karssemeijer et al. (2017) reported positive effects of physical exercise training on cognitive function in dementia found that out of 10 RCTs the average age of participants was 72 years, and all were at least ≥ 65 years meaning they must be considered as LOD. Similarly, studies in a meta-analysis by Heyn et al. (2004) were limited to those involving participants 65 and over. In this context, the scoping review by Rodgers et al. (2018) stated more research is needed to identify exercise needs for people with YOD. YOD and LOD are different and efficacious exercise interventions in LOD may not be so in YOD (Millenaar et al., 2016) as better fitness levels in those with YOD leaves less margin for improvement (Beattie et al., 2004). In a recent scoping review, Mettelinge et al. (2021) reported no studies that have focussed on the effect of aerobic exercise on physical fitness, cognition, or mental health in YOD. Further to that, a review by Aplaon et al. (2016) found no results for resistance-based interventions in YOD. Exercise’s impact in people with YOD is poorly understood. However, before applying an exercise intervention in people with YOD, we thought it pragmatic to conduct a case-

control study to see specifically which physiological systems were inferior to controls. This would provide insight into which exercise may be most targeted for people with YOD.

Aims and Hypothesis

Therefore, the aim of this study was to compare physical outcomes (estimated $\dot{V}O_{2max}$, body composition, blood pressure, vascular function, muscle architecture, lung function, handgrip strength and physical activity), cognitive outcomes (dexterity and fine motor skills and cognitive function) and psychological outcomes (mental and cognitive wellbeing) in people with YOD to age- and sex-matched controls. We hypothesised via theoretical deduction that BMI, blood pressure, vascular function, muscle architecture, lung function, estimated $\dot{V}O_{2max}$, physical activity, dexterity and fine motor skills, cognitive function and mental and cognitive wellbeing would be inferior in people with YOD compared to controls.

5. Methods

Participants

For our sample size calculation, the primary outcome measure was estimated aerobic capacity derived from the Astrand-Rhyming cycle ergometer test (Astrand and Rhyming, 1954) and we used the ‘pwr’ package in R studio ((R, version 4.2.2, Boston, USA) to complete the calculation. Using the minimum clinically significant difference for aerobic capacity of 1-MET ($3.5 \text{ mL}\cdot\text{kg}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$), a standard deviation of $3.6 \text{ mL}\cdot\text{kg}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$, a desired statistical power of 0.80 and an α value of 0.05, this resulted in a sample of $n=17$ per group. Therefore, we aimed to recruit $n=20$ per group to allow for a 15% drop-out rate, resulting in 40 participants in total. On completion of the study, 33 participants, 16 in the YOD group and 17 in the control group, were included, 20 of which were male and 13 were female. Our intention was to recruit 17 in both groups however, one of the YOD participants dropped out after recruitment due to injury which unrelated to the study. The NHS Lanarkshire Young Onset Dementia service was used as a participant identification centre (PIC) for the study and information was shared with patients during their consultations. Ethical approval was gained from the NHS London Riverside Ethics Committee (22/LO/0687) and the proposed study was deemed to have minimal risks to researchers and participants (Appendix 1). The study conforms to the declaration of Helsinki and good clinical practice (GCP). Once potential participants were identified, contact details of the university were provided to them. For this study, HRA approval was not sought and UWS sponsored the research. This study was not preregistered as it was not a clinical trial. Those who registered interest were given a participant information sheet (PIS) (Appendix 2) which included information regarding the purpose of the study and what will be expected of them during data collection. A letter of invitation (Appendix 3) was then sent out to all participants as well as demonstration videos of all the tests. Written informed consent (Appendix 4) was obtained as well as a Physical Activity Readiness Questionnaire (PAR-Q) (Appendix 5). To be included, participants had to be over the age of 18 and have been diagnosed with YOD or over the age of 18 and have no YOD diagnosis. The exclusion criteria were based on the participant answering ‘yes’ to any of the PAR-Q questions.

The study comprised of two components, a remote aspect where questionnaires were completed via a web app and an in-person aspect attending the University of the West of Scotland's Lanarkshire campus. Each participant had travel expenses covered and an individual time slot of approximately two hours for laboratory testing was allotted. Guidance on appropriate clothing and adequate hydration was provided and carers were welcome to attend. Participants and carers were provided with seating and a quiet room. The participant, carer, and research team were the only ones with access to the laboratory during data collection. Consent was reconfirmed with each participant and a short wellbeing interview was conducted.

Table 1: Descriptive data of participants at enrolment.

Variable	Group	Mean \pm SD	T-test p value and Cohen's <i>d</i>
Age (years)	YOD (n = 16)	60 \pm 7	p=0.577
	Control (n= 17)	58 \pm 10	<i>d</i> = 0.20
Stature (cm)	YOD (n = 16)	167 \pm 7	p = 0.487
	Control (n= 17)	169 \pm 7	<i>d</i> = 0.25
Body Mass (kg)	YOD (n = 16)	79.2 \pm 16.5	p = 0.501
	Control (n= 17)	83.6 \pm 20.9	<i>d</i> = 0.24
Body Mass Index (kg/m ²)	YOD (n = 16)	28 \pm 5	p = 0.631
	Control (n= 17)	29 \pm 6	<i>d</i> = 0.17
Systolic blood pressure (mmHg)	YOD (n = 16)	150 \pm 19	p = 0.365
	Control (n= 17)	143 \pm 24	<i>d</i> = 0.32

Diastolic blood pressure (mmHg)	YOD (n = 16)	83 ± 9	p = 0.465
	Control (n= 17)	81 ± 10	d = 0.26
Resting Heart Rate (bpm)	YOD (n = 16)	76 ± 11	p = 0.751
	Control (n= 17)	75 ± 15	d = 0.17

Laboratory Testing Protocol

Estimated $\dot{V}O_{2max}$

The aerobic capacity was assessed using the submaximal Astrand-Rhyming test (Astrand and Rhyming, 1954), this is a single stage aerobic capacity test carried out for six minutes on a Watt bike cycle ergometer (ProTrainer, Wattbike, England). This test was selected as aerobic capacity was our primary outcome variable however, it was not feasible to use a maximal $\dot{V}O_{2max}$ test in this clinical population and as such a submaximal equivalent was selected. This test has been shown in previous literature to have an intraclass correlation coefficient of 0.94 indicating excellent reliability (Lennon et al., 2011), meaning that Astrand-Rhyming tests are highly consistent when repeated over time further justifying our choice for the present study. Each participant was fitted with a chest strap heart rate (HR) monitor (PC.15.11, SIGMA, Germany) and the ergometer was adjusted (saddle height, tilt, and handlebar height) to avoid injury and ensure comfort. Heart rate at rest was recorded on a score sheet and then the participant was assisted to mount the ergometer. The HR range for the test was between 125-175 b·min⁻¹ (low-moderate intensity exercise). The participant performed a three-minute warm up with the ergometer at a resistance of zero, after three minutes the resistance was adjusted aiming to illicit the target HR range and the test started. In the first two minutes of the test the resistance was allowed to be adjusted, after this no further adjustment was allowed. HR and wattage were recorded for every minute of the test using a stopwatch (Fast time 2, United Kingdom) and scoresheet. If the HR was within five b·min⁻¹ for minute five and six the values were noted and the test was concluded, if not the resistance

was adjusted, and a further minute performed, if HR range was still not achieved then a further six minutes was performed. The test was deemed successful once the participant completed the full six minutes and reached the target HR within five $\text{b}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ for the last two minutes. The participant was subject to constant wellbeing monitoring throughout and if needed the exercise testing was to be stopped in accordance with the ACSM guidelines for exercise termination (Liguori, 2020). Participants then performed a one-minute cool down and were assisted to dismount the ergometer. During analysis the average HR of the last two minutes performed was plotted in the Astrand-Rhyming Nomogram (Astrand and Rhyming, 1954), this was plotted against the wattage and $\dot{V}\text{O}_2$ in $\text{mL}\cdot\text{kg}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ was predicted. The appropriate age correction factor applied to obtain a final aerobic capacity estimation.

Body Composition

Stature was measured using a wall mounted stadiometer (SECA, CE0123, Germany), shown to have a intraclass correlation coefficient of 0.9 (Geeta et al., 2009), indicating excellent reliability and highlighting that this measure is consistent across time. Participants removed their shoes and stood in the anatomical position keeping a straight back and ensuring their heels were in contact with the floor, stature was recorded in centimetres. Body mass of each participant was recorded using electronic scales (SECA 876, CE0123, Germany), shown to have an excellent reliability with an intraclass correlation coefficient level of 0.94-0.98 (Kumar et al., 2014). Participants wore minimal clothing (shorts and t shirt), and body mass was recorded in kilograms. Body composition determination was conducted in accordance with the International Society for the Assessment of Kinanthropometry (ISAK) (Garrido-Chamorro et al., 2012). Each participant's BMI was then calculated ($\text{BMI} = \text{kg}/\text{m}^2$) from the body composition values.

Blood Pressure

Resting blood pressure (BP) of participants was measured using an automated sphygmomanometer (Omron, the Netherlands), in accordance with the international society of hypertension (ISH) protocol (Unger et al., 2020). Previous ICC values of 0.81 have been seen when measuring systolic BP using this method (Lim et al., 2019). The participant was seated, and the BP cuff was secured on their left

arm, a few centimetres above the elbow crease. The machine was then initialised, and the cuff inflated to 200 mmHg and subsequently deflated to 0 mmHg, this process was repeated three times and recorded. A one-minute rest period between repetitions was used, deemed optimal for BP accuracy by Eguchi et al., (2009).

Vascular Function

Vascular endothelial function was assessed via ultrasound scan of the brachial artery. This was done using flow mediated dilation (FMD) of the brachial artery, high resolution B-mode ultrasound imaging was performed with a 12 MHz linear transducer (Vivid I, GE, Healthcare, Horton, Norway) and a rapid cuff inflator (Hockanson, Washington, USA). The participant was in the supine position on a plinth with their right arm abducted to 90⁰ while a short non-branching segment of the brachial artery proximal to the antecubital fossa was imaged, a large pneumatic cuff was attached to their upper forearm. Initially, one minute of baseline data to ascertain brachial artery diameter and doppler flow was collected with the transducer held longitudinally and after this the cuff was inflated to 180 mmHg for five minutes using a rapid cuff inflator (Hockanson, Washington, USA). It was then deflated and four minutes of post deflation artery diameters and doppler flow data was recorded. The images were captured, and arterial diameter, flow and shear were assessed using semi-automated edge detection software (Brachial Analyzer, Medical Imaging Applications LLC, Coralville, IA). The software tracked the vessel walls and blood velocity trace in B-mode frames initially, a clear region of interest (ROI) is set where there is obvious on-screen distinction between the artery walls and the lumen. Once the ROI is established the software can run automatic analysis absent from user bias. The brachial artery diameter and blood velocity data were transferred onto excel (Excel, version 2301, Microsoft, Redmond, WA). Shear stress and arterial diameter averaged over three second periods were calculated. The absolute (mm), relative (%) ($\text{Relative FMD (\%)} = \frac{\text{Post-stimulus diameter} - \text{Baseline diameter}}{\text{Baseline diameter}} \times 100$) was calculated and exported to excel.

Muscle Architecture

Muscle architecture of each subject was determined using ultrasound images of the resting vastus lateralis (VL) muscle. The test was completed with the participant in the supine position on a plinth a 7-10 MHz, 4.7cm linear array transducer fitted in the Vivid I equipment (Vivid I, GE, Healthcare, Horton, Norway). Scans were then taken at the distal third of the VL upwards on the mid sagittal axis of the VL. This area was defined as 35% of the way between the greater trochanter and the distal part of the femoral condyle, the condyle is the 0% mark, and the greater trochanter is the 100% mark. The femur length was measured using a measuring tape (SECA 201, Germany) and the 35% mark was marked on the leg via marker pen. The transducer was placed on the skin with the distal border in contact with the marked area and images were captured. Muscle architecture was mapped via the fascicle length, defined as the distance between fascicle insertions at the deep and superficial aponeurosis, muscle thickness defined as the length between the deep and superficial aponeurosis and pennation angle defined as the angle between the fascicle and tendon axis using ImageJ software (version 1.42q, National Institute of Health, USA). Fascicle length was measured three times and averaged, in the case that a full fascicle was not visible it was extrapolated given that 50% of the fascicle was visible. The image was expanded in preview (MacOS Ventura, Apple, USA) and the superficial and deep aponeurosis were extended in accordance with the Ticinesi et al., (2018) protocol, the fascicle length was then measured. The muscle thickness was measured three times and then averaged; the fascicle length divided by the muscle thickness was equal to the ultrasound sarcopenia index (USI). Inferences were made in accordance with Narici et al. (2021) and subjects were classified as non-sarcopenic when $USI < 3.70-4.23$, pre sarcopenic when $USI = 4.23-4.76$, moderately sarcopenic when $USI = 4.76-5.29$, sarcopenic when $USI = 5.29-5.82$ and severely sarcopenic when $USI > 5.82$.

Lung Function

A plastic peak flow meter (Mini Wright, PEA001, Clement Clarke, New York, USA), was used to assess the participants lung function. Participants were asked to sit down on a chair/plinth in the laboratory, relax, and perform a maximal inhalation before a subsequent maximal exhalation as quick and forceful as possible. Measurement of peak flow were shown on the plastic dial of the meter and recorded for the subject's score. Participants performed three trials allowing a one-minute rest between

trials in accordance with the American Thoracic Society (ATS) (Miller et al., 2005). This rest period was given to mitigate against localised fatigue in the respiratory muscles. The three measurements taken were averaged to obtain a final value. The peak flow meter used (Mini Wright, PEA001, Clement Clarke, New York, USA), has been shown to have an intraclass correlation coefficient of 0.87 when collecting peak flow measurements (Fonseca et al., 2005), indicating good reliability.

Functional Capacity (Handgrip Strength Test)

Functional capacity was assessed using the handgrip strength test. This test was completed using a handgrip dynamometer (Takei Scientific Instruments, Japan). This was carried out in the sitting position in accordance with the Southampton protocol (Roberts et al., 2011). The participant held the dynamometer in their dominant hand and kept their arms by their sides, the hand holding the dynamometer was kept at 90°. It was adjusted to zero and the participant was asked to squeeze it as hard as possible for 5-10s, three trials were completed with one-minute intervals between trials and the best score recorded.

Physical Activity (ActiGraph GT3X+)

Participants were asked to wear an wGT3X-BT ActiGraph accelerometer (ActiGraph LLC, Pensacola, FL, USA) on their self-reported non-dominant wrist. Prior to distribution, all accelerometer devices were initialised in ActiLife v6.13.4 (ActiGraph, Pensacola, FL, USA) to collect data at 100 Hz, and commence data collection shortly after distribution. The “idle sleep mode” in ActiLife v6.13.4 was not enabled. Participants were instructed to wear the device 24 hours per day for a seven-day period, only removing the device during water-based activities (swimming, bathing, and showering).

Once devices were returned, data were downloaded as raw .gt3x files which were subsequently processed using the GGIR package version 3.0-5 in R statistical software (R Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria, <http://cran.r-project.org/>; Migueles, Rowlands, et al., 2019). In GGIR, files were processed to detect abnormally high values, detect nonwear (Migueles, Rowlands, et al., 2019), and calibrated using local gravity as a reference (van Hees et al., 2014). Files were excluded from subsequent analyses if post calibration error was >0.01 g, or if participants had less than one valid

wear day (defined as ≥ 16 hr per day) or wear data was not present for each 15-min period of the 24-hr cycle (Buchan, 2022). The default nonwear setting was applied during processing within GGIR (van Hees et al., 2013).

Alongside wear time (days), the time spent inactive (< 30 mg; Bakrania et al., 2016), in light physical activity (LPA) (between 30 and 100 mg) and moderate-vigorous physical activity (MVPA) (> 100 mg; Hilderbrand et al., (2014)) was provided. Inactive time is provided exclusive of sleep time after applying the automated Heuristic Algorithm looking at Change of Z-Angle (HDCZA) algorithm within GGIR as previously described (van Hees et al., 2018; Buchan et al., 2024). For participants to be included in subsequent analysis, they had to provide a minimum of four days (three weekdays and one weekend day) as recommended (Migueles et al., 2017).

Dexterity and Fine Motor Skills

The Purdue Pegboard Test (PPBT) was used to test fingertip dexterity and gross movements of the hand, fingers, and arm. This was completed using a pegboard (Patterson Medical, China) on an adequately sized table. This is a standardised test involving four stages and tasks, the participant was given a full overview of the tests and was allotted time to practice each of these before the test was administered. The first task was to insert pegs into vertical holes using their dominant hand which was timed to 30s by a stopwatch (Fast time 2, United Kingdom). The same task was repeated using the non-dominant hand for 30s and then repeated using both hands for 30s, these three scores were then summed together to give the left + right + both final scores. The final task required inserting the peg into the board using their dominant hand while also placing a washer over it using their non-dominant hand which was followed by inserting a bolt on top of it using the dominant hand and placing a washer on top using their non-dominant hand, forming an assembly. This was timed to one minute and each individual piece placed on the board was counted as one during scoring. The score at the end of each task was recorded and three trials were carried out and then averaged to produce final scores. This was then compared to standardised guidelines (Lindstrom-Hazel and Veenstra, 2015).

Cognitive Function

Cognitive function was measured using Addenbrooke's Cognitive Examination (ACE-III). This consisted of 19 activities which measure five cognitive domains: attention, memory, fluency, language, and visuospatial processing. Attention was assessed by asking the participant to state the year and season as well as a continuous subtraction exercise. Memory was tested by recalling three words after memorising them and recalling renowned historical facts. Fluency was assessed by asking the participant to repeat as many words as possible that began with a specific letter in one minute. Language was tested by challenging the participant to write two grammatically correct sentences. Lastly, the visuospatial domain was assessed by drawing a clock face with the hands set at a specified time. The test took approximately 15 minutes to administer and five minutes to score. The maximum score was 100 with a greater score being indicative of higher cognitive functioning. The consensus within the literature as a threshold for dementia diagnosis is a score of 82-88/100 (Beishon et al., 2019). This method has shown excellent reliability (ICC= 0.92) in detecting cognitive impairment (Takenoshita et al., 2019).

Mental and Cognitive Wellbeing

The second segment of the remote data collection involved the participants completing online questionnaires based on mental and cognitive wellbeing, this was completed via Microsoft Forms (Forms, Microsoft, Redmond, WA). The forms software was used to create online versions of validated questionnaires based on anxiety, depression, self-efficacy, sleepiness, health related quality of life and measures of health which helped us establish the mental and cognitive wellbeing of each participant. The first of the online questionnaires was the general anxiety disorder assessment (GAD-7), this is a seven item self-report anxiety questionnaire. It takes ~five minutes to complete and enquires about the degree to which the participant felt worried, anxious, on edge or restless over the previous two weeks of life. It has been previously validated in the literature (Spitzer et al., 2006). It is scored by each item being rated from 0-3 (0= not at all, 3= every day), with the maximum score being 21. A score of five represents mild anxiety, 10 represents moderate and 15 represents severe anxiety.

The second questionnaire was the patient health questionnaire (PHQ-9) which is a nine-item tool based around screening, diagnosing, monitoring, and measuring depression. The nine items focus on the Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders 4th Edition (DSM-IV) (Bell, 1994). The questions are based around the degree to which the participant has been affected by each of the nine items over the past two weeks, like the GAD-7 and takes ~three minutes to complete. It has been previously validated by Sun et al., (2020). It is scored by each item being rated 0-3 (0= not at all, 3= every day), the total score was between 0-27 with 5-9 rated as mild depression, 10-14 rated as moderate and ≥ 20 as severe.

The European quality of life five-dimension (EQ-5D-3L) questionnaire was used to evaluate the participants general quality of life. This consisted of five components focussed on their health-related quality of life. It takes ~2-3 minutes to complete and has questions relating to mobility, pain, discomfort, anxiety, and depression. The participants also rate their health out of 100 using a visual analogue scale (VAS). This has been previously validated by Hernandez et al., (2019). It is scored by the participant rating each component from 0-3 which gives a five-dimension profile score, this is then used to compute an index score on a scale of 0-1 with higher scores indicating better health. The VAS (0-100) is also considered, and higher scores are indicative of better health related quality of life.

The self-efficacy scale (GSE) was used to assess participant optimism, this is a 10-item psychometric scale designed to assess the optimistic self-beliefs of the individual. Responses are marked on a four-point Likert scale. The questions are based around participants beliefs around difficult scenarios in life. It has been validated by Löve, Dea Moore and Hensing (2012). A score on a scale of 10-40 can be derived from the results with higher score indicating better perceived self-efficacy and lower scores indicating poor perceived self-efficacy.

To assess sleep quality the Pittsburgh sleep quality index (PSQI) was used, this is a self-report questionnaire assessing the quality of sleep over a 1-month period, it consists of 19 individual items split to seven components which give a single score. The seven components consist of subjective sleep quality, sleep latency, sleep duration, habitual sleep efficiency, sleep disturbances, medication, and daytime dysfunction. The questionnaire takes ~five minutes to complete and has been validated

by Backhaus et al., (2002). Each of the seven components are scored 0-3 and summed at the end for a maximum score of 21, the higher the score is indicative of poorer sleep quality. When they attended the lab for testing each participant and their carer was guided by one of the research team on how to access and complete the questionnaires, subsequently the links were emailed to them. Remote delivery took ~one hour including access and walkthroughs.

Statistical Analysis

Analyses were conducted using the R Studio software (R, version 4.2.2, Boston, USA). Firstly, a Shapiro-wilk test of normality and Levene's test of equal variance were conducted. Once both assumptions were confirmed, an independent T-tests were conducted (YOD v controls). If data did not meet assumptions of normality and equal variance, the Mann-Whitney U nonparametric test was deployed. Alpha levels are reported as p values as per the American Statistical Association recommendations (Hurlbert, Levine and Utts, 2019). Effect sizes are reported as Cohen's *d* for pairwise comparisons and were interpreted as small (≥ 0.2), medium (≥ 0.5), and large (≥ 0.8) (Lakens, 2013). All figures were produced using the ggplot2 package in R studio (R, version 4.2.2, Boston, USA) and displayed as grouped dot plots displaying the mean line for data which passed parametric assumptions or median line for data which violated assumptions as recommended by Drummond and Vowler (2011) and Weissgerber et al. (2015). Data are presented in the text as mean \pm SD. Inferences were made based on a combination of p values, mean differences, and effect sizes. Our primary outcome variable was estimated $\dot{V}O_{2\max}$, so the study is only powered to detect an α value of 0.05 for that variable.

6. Results

Estimated $\dot{V}O_{2max}$

Estimated $\dot{V}O_{2max}$ data was normally distributed with equal variance. There was no difference in estimated $\dot{V}O_{2max}$ at the $p < 0.05$ level between groups, despite the moderate effect size ($p = 0.119$, $d = 0.7$). This test experienced some reluctance from some participants to complete exercise on the bike and technical difficulties related to heart rate monitors hence the lower numbers in comparison to subsequent tests.

Figure 1. Estimated $\dot{V}O_{2max}$ data from people with young onset dementia (YOD; $n = 13$) and controls ($n = 11$) from a submaximal Astrand-Rhyming test. Data are presented as individual dot plots with accompanying mean line.

Vascular Function

Vascular function data was normally distributed with equal variance on both parameters. The t-test analysis found there were no differences between groups on both parameters (baseline diameter (mm) $p = 0.162$, $d = 0.5$; moderate effect, brachial artery flow mediated dilation % $p = 0.118$, $d = 0.6$; moderate effect).

Figure 2. Vascular function parameters from people with young onset dementia (YOD; n = 16) and controls (n = 17). Data are presented as individual dot plots with accompanying mean line.

Muscle Architecture

Muscle architecture data violated the assumption of normal distribution on one parameter (Shapiro-Wilk test of normality, muscle thickness $p = 0.032$) and met the assumption of equal variance for all parameters. The Mann Whitney U and t-test analysis found there were differences present in fascicle length ($p = 0.028$, $d = 0.81$; large effect), with a mean difference of 7.64 mm and no differences in muscle thickness ($p = 0.228$, $d = 0.26$; small effect), pennation angle ($p = 0.678$, $d = 0.15$; trivial effect), or USI ($p = 0.702$, $d = 0.14$; trivial effect).

Figure 3. Muscle architecture parameters from people with young onset dementia (YOD; $n = 16$) and controls ($n = 17$). Data are presented as individual dot plots with accompanying mean line (fascicle length, pennation angle and USI) and median line (muscle thickness). Significance is denoted by ‘*’ within figures.

Lung Function

Lung function data was normally distributed, with equal variance. The t-test analysis revealed there was no difference in peak flow between groups ($p = 0.496$, $d = 0.24$; small effect).

Figure 4. Peak flow data from people with young onset dementia (YOD; n = 16) and controls (n = 17). Data are presented as individual dot plots with accompanying mean line.

Functional Capacity (Handgrip Strength Test)

Handgrip data was found to be normally distributed and to have equal variance. The t-test analysis found there was no difference in handgrip strength between the groups ($p = 0.284$, $d = 0.39$; small effect).

Figure 5. Handgrip strength data from people with young onset dementia (YOD; n = 16) and controls (n = 17). Data are presented as individual dot plots with accompanying mean line.

Physical Activity (ActiGraph GT3X+)

Physical activity data violated the assumption of normal distribution on some parameters (Shapiro-Wilk test of normality, sedentary $p < 0.001$) and had equal variance. There were differences in sedentary time ($p = 0.029$, $d = 0.54$; moderate effect), with a mean difference of 74.2 counts per minute. There were also differences in MVPA ($p = 0.014$, $d = 0.97$; large effect), with a mean difference of 35.20 counts per minute. However, no differences in LPA ($p = 0.440$, $d = 0.31$; small effect) between the groups.

Figure 6. Physical activity parameters from people with young onset dementia (YOD; n = 16) and controls (n = 17). Data are presented as individual dot plots with accompanying mean line (LPA and MVPA) and median line (sedentary time). Significance is denoted by ‘*’ within figures.

Dexterity and Fine Motor Skills

Dexterity and fine motor skills data violated the assumption of normal distribution on some parameters (Shapiro-Wilk test of normality, right hand p = 0.010) and equal variance on some parameters (Levene’s test of variance, left hand p = 0.007). The Mann-Whitney U and t-test analysis revealed there were large differences on all dexterity parameters (left p = 0.013, d = 1.0; large effect, right p = 0.008, d = 1.0; large effect, both p <0.001, d = 1.40; large effect, Left + right + both p <0.001, d = 1.30; large effect, assembly p <0.001, d = 1.60; large effect). The mean differences were 2.41 on left hand, 2.48 on right hand, 3.35 on both hands, 8.11 on left + right + both hands and 10.55 on the assembly.

Figure 7. Dexterity and fine motor skills parameters from the Purdue Pegboard Test in people with young onset dementia (YOD; $n = 16$) and controls ($n = 17$). Data are presented as individual dot plots with accompanying mean line (both hands, left + right + both hands and assembly) and median line (left hand and right hand). Significance is denoted by ‘*’ within figures.

Cognitive Function

The cognitive function data violated the assumption of normal distribution on some parameters (Shapiro-Wilk test of normality, attention $p = 0.013$, language $p = 0.033$, visuospatial $p < 0.001$) and equal variance on some parameters (Levene’s test of variance, attention $p = 0.018$, memory $p < 0.001$, fluency $p < 0.001$, language $p < 0.001$, visuospatial $p < 0.001$, total score $p < 0.001$). The Mann-Whitney U and t-test analysis revealed there were large differences on all cognitive function parameters (attention $p < 0.001$, $d = 2.34$; large effect, memory $p < 0.001$, $d = 3.90$; large effect, fluency $p < 0.001$, $d = 3.0$; large effect, language $p < 0.001$, $d = 1.70$; large effect, visuospatial $p < 0.001$, $d = 1.09$; large

effect, total score $p < 0.001$, $d = 3.60$; large effect). There was a mean difference of 40.2 on total ACE-III score between groups

Figure 8. Cognitive function parameters from people with young onset dementia (YOD; $n = 16$) and controls ($n = 17$). Data are presented as individual dot plots with accompanying median line. Significance is denoted by ‘*’ within figures.

GAD-7

GAD-7 violated normal distribution (Shapiro-Wilk test of normality, $p = 0.003$) and variance (Levene’s test of variance, $p = 0.047$). The Mann Whitney U analysis found there was no difference in GAD-7 scores between the groups ($p = 0.483$, $d = 0.15$; small effect).

EQ-5D-3L

EQ-5D-3L data had normal distribution on some parameters and equal variance. The t-test analysis found there were differences present in analog scores between groups ($p = 0.007$, $d = 1.10$; large effect), with a mean difference between groups of 10 and no differences for index scores between groups ($p = 0.137$, $d = 0.57$; moderate effect). Significance is denoted by ‘*’ within figures.

Figure 11. EQ-5D-3L parameters from people with young onset dementia (YOD; $n = 16$) and controls ($n = 17$). Data are presented as individual dot plots with accompanying mean line.

GSE

GSE data was found to be normally distributed but had unequal variance (Levene’s test of variance, $p = 0.016$). The Mann-Whitney U analysis found controls had a greater GSE score than the YOD group ($p < 0.001$, $d = 1.29$; large effect), with a mean difference of 8.2. Significance is denoted by ‘*’ within figures.

7. Discussion

Main Findings

The aim of the present study was to compare physical outcomes (estimated $\dot{V}O_{2max}$, body composition, blood pressure, vascular function, muscle architecture, lung function, handgrip strength and physical activity), cognitive outcomes (dexterity and fine motor skills and cognitive function) and psychological outcomes (mental and cognitive wellbeing) in people with YOD to age- and sex-matched controls. We hypothesised *a priori* that BMI, blood pressure, vascular function, muscular health, lung function, estimated $\dot{V}O_{2max}$, physical activity, dexterity and fine motor skills, cognitive function, and mental and cognitive wellbeing would be lesser in people with YOD compared to controls. Herein, we report differences between the YOD group and control group in fascicle length, sedentary time, MVPA, dexterity and fine motor skills, cognitive function, EQ-5D-3L analog score, and GSE score. There were no differences between groups in estimated $\dot{V}O_{2max}$, vascular function, pennation angle, muscle thickness, USI, lung function, functional capacity, sedentary time and LPA, GAD-7 score, PHQ-9 score, EQ-5D-3L index score, and PSQI score.

Interpretation of Findings

In the present study, it was found the YOD group performed worse than controls on the Purdue pegboard test. Although the evidence base in YOD is lacking, these findings agree with previous literature that found LOD patients performed inferior compared to cognitively healthy adults (Menegic et al., 2023). It was also found in this study that the YOD group performed significantly inferior than controls on the ACE-III. It is likely that both findings are related. Due to declining cognitive function in those with dementia because of the different pathologies, participation in activities of daily living decrease, leading to a reduction in functional independence and a worsening of dexterity and bimanual coordination (De Paula et al., 2016).

The findings of this study showed fascicle length of the vastus lateralis to be shorter in the YOD group compared to controls. A difference in fascicle length of this magnitude may suggest a greater predisposition to frailty in those with YOD (Mpampoulis et al., 2021). However, in previous work by

Narici et al. (2021), it was concluded that while fascicle length is important, measures of frailty are more closely linked to the thickness of the muscle. It is likely that the differences observed in fascicle length in the present study are attributed to innate factors and not to frailty (Fukutani and Kurihara, 2015) however, more investigative research is needed in YOD to confirm this.

In the present study YOD participants were significantly more sedentary than controls. This finding could potentially be explained by dementia type. For example, some dementia types such as AD can increase risk of seizures in those diagnosed (Pandis and Scarmeas, 2012). This may discourage people from being active as they may fear aggravating this symptom (Hommet et al., 2008) and may explain the increased sedentary time in YOD disproportionate to age matched controls. However, more research is needed into specific dementia types in YOD to confirm this finding. Further to this, YOD participants completed significantly less MVPA than control participants. This low level of vigorous activity suggests a heightened risk of obesity and diabetes in YOD populations (Park et al., 2020). Due to reduced cognitive function those with YOD may complete less physical activity either because they forget or become more isolated (Rodgers et al., 2018). Therefore, the likelihood of them participating in MVPA is reduced, as shown in the study by Long et al., (2020).

The present study found the EQ-5D-3L analog score was inferior in the YOD group compared to the control group. These findings are consistent with previous research which has found similar results (Dixit et al., 2021). The reason for this disparity in health rating between the groups is likely caused by the sudden loss of independence post YOD diagnosis, those with YOD become reliant on caregivers to maintain their lives and as such their perception of their own health goes into decline (Rodgers et al., 2018). The study also found GSE scores to be lower in the YOD group. This is consistent with previous literature that has found GSE scores tend to be inferior in YOD groups (Rossor et al., 2010). This is likely down to those in the YOD groups perceptions of their capacity declining, after diagnosis they lose confidence in their ability to control their lives and situations due to cognitive decline (Tonga et al., 2020). It is clear in the existing literature that the EQ-5D-3L and GSE scores are related, a study by Tran et al., (2007) found that in patients with chronic conditions those with a lower GSE score generally have a lower EQ-5D-3L score. The present study reveals a marked difference in variance between the

YOD group and the control group across various tests. The control group exhibits a smaller variance, likely due to its more homogeneous composition. In contrast, the YOD group, characterized by a broader range of symptoms inherent to their diagnosis (Kuruppu and Matthews., 2014), demonstrates greater variability in their results, leading to a wider spread in the data.

Despite the marked differences listed above, there were also several variables where no differences were found between groups. For example, estimated $\dot{V}O_{2max}$ was not different at the $p < 0.05$ level between groups. However, estimated $\dot{V}O_{2max}$ was still $5.34 \text{ mL}\cdot\text{kg}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ greater in controls than the YOD group. A difference in estimated $\dot{V}O_{2max}$ of this magnitude would suggest a greater risk of diabetes and cardiovascular disease in YOD populations (Bye et al., 2013). A meta-analysis by Kodama et al. (2009) showed that a 1-MET ($3.5 \text{ mL}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$) increase in $\dot{V}O_{2max}$ was associated with a 13% and 15% reduction in risk of all-cause mortality and CVD, respectively. This finding is likely the result of reduced cardiovascular efficiency seen in some dementias (Brain et al., 2023) resulting in decreased oxygen delivery to the muscle or carrying capacity in the blood which reduces $\dot{V}O_{2max}$. Despite not being $p < 0.05$ in the present study, due to the strong link between $\dot{V}O_{2max}$ and overall health and wellbeing, this finding may still warrant further consideration in future studies and structured interventions for the clinical group.

Vascular function was similar across both study groups, these findings are like previous studies which have directly measured FMD in those with dementia (Garg et al., 2020). However, previous research has shown a specific link between endothelial dysfunction and AD due to the reduced availability of nitric oxide which can exacerbate amyloid levels (Tachibana et al., 2016). While our findings do not fall in line with this previous work, it is possible this is due to our smaller sample ($n = 16$) or the fact the YOD group are younger than participants from previous research, vascular function is likely higher in terms of baseline diameter and reactivity regardless of diagnosis (Tsao et al., 2013). The present study found that while fascicle length was different between groups, in the remaining muscle architecture parameters there were no observed differences. Despite this, previous work has found that sarcopenia, which is the age-related loss of muscle mass and importantly function is prevalent in those

with dementia due to reductions in grey matter leading to a reduction in physical capacity which sets off a cascade of inactivity and exacerbation of muscle atrophy particularly in the lower extremities (Waite et al., 2021). That said, previous research on muscle architecture in dementia primarily focuses on LOD and it is important to consider the age of the YOD group (*range = 35-64*). It is likely due to the variety in age that sarcopenia is less likely to influence participants at this age, despite what has been observed in LOD (Walston, 2012).

Lung function was not different between the two groups. Previous research has shown that reduced peak flow has been linked to dementia as this causes systemic inflammation and hypoxia which can lead to neuronal death (Xiao et al., 2021). Despite these findings in previous literature, much of this evidence is based on LOD and it is possible YOD groups do not experience this deficiency in lung function like LOD, however more research is required to confirm our observation. It should also be noted in our study much of the YOD sample were medicated with common dementia drugs such as donepezil and rivastigmine both of which have been shown in the literature to have anti-inflammatory properties which may have confounded the results of the present study (Kim et al., 2021). It is also possible the order of the laboratory testing had an impact on the results as YOD participants in particular may have been fatigued by the time they reached this point in the battery. Our study found that handgrip strength was not different between groups. Previous research has shown those with dementia have inferior handgrips strength compared to normative values (Alencar et al., 2012) however, these findings are in older adults where handgrip strength is likely to be lesser due to the reduced demand on extremities and reduction in activities attributed to age (Vermeulen et al., 2015), this study was however, still age matched suggesting an age x dementia interaction. Much of the YOD sample in this study were still in employment and therefore used their hands more often which may explain our findings.

Despite the YOD group being more sedentary and the control group completing more MVPA than the YOD group, there were no differences between groups for sedentary time or LPA. This may be explained by the fact that much of the YOD group were recently diagnosed due to our recruitment strategy and as such are still active members of their community who complete LPA (Rodgers et al., 2018).

There were no differences between groups for the GAD-7, PHQ-9 and PSQI questionnaires. This may be explained by reasons highlighted previously that are attributed to their age and stage of the diagnosis, perhaps some of the ailments associated with dementia have yet to set in (Draper and Whittall, 2016). However, it is possible due to the self-report nature of the questionnaires that there is bias at play. Previous research by Dixit et al., (2021) demonstrated that those with YOD due to impaired cognition are unlikely to give accurate reports on their own daily functioning and this may explain our finding in the present study.

Implications for Exercise Interventions and Future Research

These aforementioned findings could be used to shape future research in YOD and to design support interventions for this population particularly focussed on exercise. As mentioned, exercise research for people with YOD is lacking and findings herein shed light upon what areas exercise research may target. For example, deficiencies were found in the YOD group across a multitude of variables including dexterity, cognitive function, muscle architecture, physical activity, and wellbeing and as such exercise interventions must take a multi- inter- or cross-disciplinary approach to tackling these problems (Rodgers et al., 2018). Previous work has demonstrated success of a multicomponent (aerobic and resistance) exercise intervention on improving cognitive function in LOD (Annika et al., 2017). Taken together with the findings from the current study it is possible a similar age adjusted protocol could exhibit benefits. The specific deficiencies identified in this study across muscle architecture, estimated $\dot{V}O_{2max}$, and physical activity further highlight the need for multicomponent interventions to target multiple wellbeing facets. Previous research has demonstrated potential for combined training to improve physical function in LOD compared to controls (Bossers et al., 2014) and it is possible these benefits could be seen in YOD. By taking a multicomponent approach and including resistance and aerobic training, specific adaptations will occur to address poorer muscle function and increase participation in physical activity (Shokri et al., 2024). Wellbeing has been shown to be improved by combined exercise protocols in LOD (Brett, Traynor and Stapley, 2016). Participation in exercise increases self-confidence and a sense of wellbeing and it is possible a structured combined training protocol could address this problem in YOD (Rodgers et al., 2018).

That said, specific exercise intervention research in YOD is lacking (Metteling et al., 2021). While it is unknown what exercise dosage may illicit the most benefits it is hoped that the findings from this study can be used for future exercise interventions to target these specific deficiencies. Future research should look to assess long-term combined exercise interventions effects on the psychological and physiological health of those with YOD. The next steps for future studies in the area could be to profile specific YOD pathologies and identify if the deficiencies found in this study are specific to any pathology and therefore paving the way for support interventions. Most importantly, longitudinal research is needed to establish the optimal frequency, intensity, time, and type to address these issues.

While exercise is an important factor, YOD support strategies should be holistic much like in LOD (Chen et al., 2023) and specific attention should be paid to the life impacts after diagnosis to ensure quality support is in place for this clinical population (Baptista et al., 2016). In our data, there did not appear to be a relationship between age and performance in the test (in the YOD group) however, future studies may look to investigate this further and on a larger scale to identify the point at which exponential deterioration in the YOD condition occurs.

Strengths and Limitations

A particular strength of the current study was the variety of variables included in the methods. The variety of testing completed allowed for a holistic profile both psychologically and physiologically of those with YOD. By adopting this inter- and multi-disciplinary approach, this study has been able to highlight the need for integrated and practical YOD interventions. A further strength of this study is the use of age and sex matched controls, which further enhances the validity of the comparisons made between the YOD and control group.

This study is not without limitations, the first being the sample size. We only recruited 16 participants to the YOD group as recruitment was performed through a participant identification centre (PIC) at the point of diagnosis. Our intended sample size was $n=17$ to detect a clinically meaningful difference ($3.5 \text{ mL}\cdot\text{kg}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$) in estimated $\dot{V}\text{O}_{2\text{max}}$ at the $p<0.05$ level. Although we did not recruit to target, estimated $\dot{V}\text{O}_{2\text{max}}$ was different with a large effect, suggesting a clinically meaningful difference between groups.

We did encounter significant dropouts due to reluctance and technical issues with heart rate monitors which may have masked true effects in this study. To quantify this, a post hoc power calculation was performed, with the measured difference in means ($5.3 \text{ mL}\cdot\text{kg}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$) and the measured standard deviation ($7.5 \text{ mL}\cdot\text{kg}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$). This power calculation, gives a sample size of $n=30$ per group to detect a change at the $p < 0.05$ level, evidencing that our study was underpowered. Prior to this study, no data existed on YOD and estimated $\dot{V}O_{2\text{max}}$, and therefore we underestimated the spread of data. Although this was of course a limitation of the present study, it does provide useful pilot data for larger studies who can utilise our central tendency and variance data for their power calculations. In an attempt to attenuate the negative influence of a relatively low sample size, we have reported magnitudes of difference throughout, rather than relying solely on p values, as recommended by the American Statistical Association (Hurlbert et al., 2019). Secondly, the participant burden may have been an issue as there were many variables to examine, potentially resulting in cognitive or physical fatigue. However, all participants followed the same testing order to control for fatigue or learning effects. This study may have also experienced some recruitment bias, due to testing requiring a laboratory visit. We are aware this is not entirely inclusive, but movement of some laboratory equipment is not possible. This study was powered to detect changes in $\dot{V}O_{2\text{max}}$ at the $p < 0.05$ level and not for the remaining variables in this study. Therefore, it is possible larger confirmatory studies investigating vascular function, muscle architecture, lung function, functional capacity and physical activity are needed to confirm these findings while accounting for analytical and biological variation. A further limitation was that the study was not preregistered, this may have benefitted the research area by aiding open science initiatives and advancing the field. The GAD-7 and GSE questionnaires although previously validated have not been validated in dementia groups and therefore we can take limited interpretation from these results. Finally, we used the Astrand-Rhyming test for predicted $\dot{V}O_{2\text{max}}$ as the Astrand-Rhyming nomogram gives a value of maximal $\dot{V}O_2$. We searched PubMed for variations of "CPET AND dementia" in an attempt to find whether people with dementia exhibit a plateau in $\dot{V}O_2$. We found one result (Salisbury and Yu, 2021) which we could not access the full text of. In some recent studies (Nordgren et al., 2014; Väisänen et al., 2020), it has been reported that the Astrand-Rhyming test is not valid to determine even maximal $\dot{V}O_{2\text{max}}$ in certain populations (e.g. the elderly or people with

rheumatoid arthritis). Thus, the Astrand-Rhyming test was originally developed to determine a maximal rather than peak value. Yet, subsequent research, as expected, has observed the values are not valid in all people. However, due to our between groups (but same test) design, we hope we have to an extent, controlled for this. We apologise we could not answer whether people with dementia exhibit a plateau in $\dot{V}O_2$, but the literature is not confirmatory at this stage.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this study provides valuable insights into the physical, cognitive, and psychological outcomes of individuals with YOD. In line with the hypothesis, findings reveal significant differences between the YOD group and controls in dexterity, cognitive function, muscle architecture, physical activity, and wellbeing measures however, there were not differences on all the parameters. These disparities underscore the multifaceted challenges faced by individuals with YOD and highlight the need for tailored support interventions, with a focus on exercise. The findings emphasise a need to put robust exercise interventions in place with a view to increasing fitness which in turn may help slow disease progression and improve overall wellbeing. Future research should focus on developing and evaluating tailored exercise protocols for individuals with YOD. The findings of this study contribute to our understanding of YOD and pave the way for further research to optimise support strategies and improve outcomes for this clinical population.

8. References

Aarsland, D. (2020) 'Epidemiology and Pathophysiology of Dementia-Related Psychosis', *The Journal of Clinical Psychiatry*, 81(5). doi:10.4088/JCP.AD19038BR1C.

Ahlskog, J.E., Geda, Y.E., Graff-Radford, N.R. and Petersen, R.C. (2011) 'Physical Exercise as a Preventive or Disease-Modifying Treatment of Dementia and Brain Aging', *Mayo Clinic Proceedings*, 86(9), pp. 876–884. doi:10.4065/mcp.2011.0252.

Alencar, M.A., Dias, J.M.D., Figueiredo, L.C. and Dias, R.C. (2012) 'Handgrip strength in elderly with dementia: study of reliability', *Brazilian Journal of Physical Therapy*, 16, pp. 510–514. doi:10.1590/S1413-35552012005000059.

Anstey, K.J., Ee, N., Eramudugolla, R., Jagger, C. and Peters, R. (2019) 'A Systematic Review of Meta-Analyses that Evaluate Risk Factors for Dementia to Evaluate the Quantity, Quality, and Global Representativeness of Evidence', *Journal of Alzheimer's Disease*. Edited by K. Anstey and R. Peters, 70(s1), pp. S165–S186. doi:10.3233/jad-190181.

Aplaon, M., Belchior, P., Gélinas, I., Bier, N. and Aboujaoudé, A. (2016) 'Interventions for Individuals with Young-Onset Dementia. A Review of the Literature', *Journal of Aging Research and Lifestyle*, pp. 1–4. doi:10.14283/jarcp.2016.123.

Åstrand, P.-O. and Ryhming, I. (1954) 'A Nomogram for Calculation of Aerobic Capacity (Physical Fitness) From Pulse Rate During Submaximal Work', *Journal of Applied Physiology*, 7(2), pp. 218–221. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1152/jappl.1954.7.2.218>.

Backhaus, J., Junghanns, K., Broocks, A., Riemann, D. and Hohagen, F. (2002) 'Test-retest reliability and validity of the Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index in primary insomnia', *Journal of psychosomatic research*, 53(3), pp. 737–40. doi:10.1016/s0022-3999(02)00330-6.

Bakrania K, Yates T, Rowlands AV, Esliger DW, Bunnewell S, Sanders J, Davies M, Khunti K, Edwardson CL. Intensity thresholds on raw acceleration data: euclidean norm

minus One (ENMO) and mean amplitude deviation (MAD) approaches. *PLoS One*. 2016;11(10):e0164045. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0164045.

Baptista, M.A.T., Santos, R.L., Kimura, N., Lacerda, I.B., Johannessen, A., Barca, M.L., Engedal, K. and Dourado, M.C.N. (2016) ‘Quality of life in young onset dementia: an updated systematic review’, *Trends in Psychiatry and Psychotherapy*, 38(1), pp. 6–13. doi:10.1590/2237-6089-2015-0049

Barnes, J.N. and Corkery, A.T. (2018) ‘Exercise Improves Vascular Function, but does this Translate to the Brain?’, *Brain Plasticity*. Edited by H. van Praag, 4(1), pp. 65–79. doi:10.3233/bpl-180075.

Beattie, A., Daker-White, G., Gilliard, J. and Means, R. (2004) “‘How can they tell?’ A qualitative study of the views of younger people about their dementia and dementia care services’, *Health and Social Care in the Community*, 12(4), pp. 359–368. doi:10.1111/j.1365-2524.2004.00505.x.

Beishon, L.C., Batterham, A.P., Quinn, T.J., Nelson, C.P., Panerai, R.B., Robinson, T. and Haunton, V.J. (2019) ‘Addenbrooke’s Cognitive Examination III (ACE-III) and mini-ACE for the detection of dementia and mild cognitive impairment’, *Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews* [Preprint]. doi:https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.cd013282.pub2.

Bell, C.C. (1994) ‘DSM-IV: Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders’, *JAMA: The Journal of the American Medical Association*, 272(10), p. 828. doi:https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.1994.03520100096046.

Borba-Pinheiro, C.J., Figueiredo, N.M.A. de, Walsh-Monteiro, A., Júnior, O.R.M. da R., Pernambuco, C.S., Oliveira, M.A. and Dantas, E.H.M. (2013) ‘Resistance training program on functional independence of an elderly man with frontotemporal dementia: a case report’, *Journal of Human Sport and Exercise*, 8(Proc2), pp. 47–53. doi:10.4100/jhse.2012.8.proc2.06.

Bossers, W.J.R., Scherder, E.J.A., Boersma, F., Hortobágyi, T., van der Woude, L.H.V. and van Heuvelen, M.J.G. (2014) ‘Feasibility of a Combined Aerobic and Strength Training Program and Its Effects on Cognitive and Physical Function in Institutionalized

Dementia Patients. A Pilot Study’, *PLoS ONE*. Edited by T.J. Quinn, 9(5), p. e97577.
Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0097577>.

Bossers, W.J.R., van der Woude, L.H.V., Boersma, F., Hortobágyi, T., Scherder, E.J.A. and van Heuvelen, M.J.G. (2015) ‘A 9-Week Aerobic and Strength Training Program Improves Cognitive and Motor Function in Patients with Dementia: A Randomized, Controlled Trial’, *The American Journal of Geriatric Psychiatry*, 23(11), pp. 1106–1116. doi:10.1016/j.jagp.2014.12.191.

Brain, J., Greene, L., Tang, E.Y.H., Louise, J., Salter, A., Beach, S., Turnbull, D., Siervo, M., Stephan, B.C.M. and Tully, P.J. (2023) ‘Cardiovascular disease, associated risk factors, and risk of dementia: An umbrella review of meta-analyses’, *Frontiers in Epidemiology*, 3. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3389/fepid.2023.1095236>.

Brodaty, H., Seeher, K. and Gibson, L. (2012) ‘Dementia time to death: a systematic literature review on survival time and years of life lost in people with dementia ‘24:7, 1034-1045 C International Psychogeriatric Association’, *International Psychogeriatrics*, 24(7). doi:10.1017/S1041610211002924.

Buchan, D. S. (2024). Comparison of Sleep and Physical Activity Metrics From Wrist-Worn ActiGraph wGT3X-BT and GT9X Accelerometers During Free-Living in Adults. *Journal for the Measurement of Physical Behaviour*, 7(1), jmpb.2023-0026. Retrieved Mar 12, 2024, from <https://doi.org/10.1123/jmpb.2023-0026>

Buchan, D.S. (2022). Equivalence of activity outcomes derived from three research grade accelerometers worn simultaneously on each wrist. *Journal of Sports Sciences*, 40(7), 797–807. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02640414.2021.2019429>

Bye, A., Røsjø, H., Aspenes, S.T., Condorelli, G., Omland, T. and Wisløff, U. (2013) ‘Circulating MicroRNAs and Aerobic Fitness – The HUNT-Study’, *PLoS ONE*. Edited by M. Fehlings, 8(2), p. e57496. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0057496>.

Cadore, E.L., Moneo, A.B.B., Mensat, M.M., Muñoz, A.R., Casas-Herrero, A., Rodriguez-Mañas, L. and Izquierdo, M. (2013) ‘Positive effects of resistance training in frail elderly patients with dementia after long-term physical restraint’, *AGE*, 36(2), pp. 801–811. doi:10.1007/s11357-013-9599-7.

Cancela, J.M., Ayán, C., Varela, S. and Seijo, M. (2016) 'Effects of a long-term aerobic exercise intervention on institutionalized patients with dementia', *Journal of Science and Medicine in Sport*, 19(4), pp. 293–298. doi:10.1016/j.jsams.2015.05.007.

Chen, Y., Hou, L., Li, Y., Lou, Y., Li, W., Struble, L.M. and Yang, H. (2023) 'Barriers and motivators to promotion of physical activity participation for older adults with mild cognitive impairment or dementia: An umbrella review', *International Journal of Nursing Studies*, p. 104493. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijnurstu.2023.104493>.

Cho, M.J., Bunsawat, K., Kim, H.J., Yoon, E.S. and Jae, S.Y. (2020) 'The acute effects of interrupting prolonged sitting with stair climbing on vascular and metabolic function after a high-fat meal', *European Journal of Applied Physiology*, 120(4), pp. 829–839. doi:10.1007/s00421-020-04321-9.

Chow, T.W., Miller, B.L., Hayashi, V.N. and Geschwind, D.H. (1999) 'Inheritance of frontotemporal dementia', *Archives of Neurology*, 56(7), pp. 817–822. doi:10.1001/archneur.56.7.817.

Coelho-Junior, H., Marzetti, E., Calvani, R., Picca, A., Arai, H. and Uchida, M. (2022) 'Resistance training improves cognitive function in older adults with different cognitive status: a systematic review and Meta-analysis', *Aging & Mental Health*, 26(2), pp. 213–224. doi:10.1080/13607863.2020.1857691.

Damirchi, A., Hosseini, F. and Babaei, P. (2017) 'Mental Training Enhances Cognitive Function and BDNF More Than Either Physical or Combined Training in Elderly Women With MCI: A Small-Scale Study', *American Journal of Alzheimer's Disease & Other Dementiasr*, 33(1), pp. 20–29. doi:10.1177/1533317517727068.

De Paula, J.J., Albuquerque, M.R., Lage, G.M., Bicalho, M.A., Romano-Silva, M.A. and Malloy-Diniz, L.F. (2016) 'Impairment of fine motor dexterity in mild cognitive impairment and Alzheimer's disease dementia: association with activities of daily living', *Revista Brasileira de Psiquiatria*, 38(3), pp. 235–238. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1590/1516-4446-2015-1874>.

Denkinger, M.D., Lindemann, U., Nicolai, S., Igl, W., Jamour, M. and Nikolaus, T. (2011) 'Assessing Physical Activity in Inpatient Rehabilitation: Validity, Practicality, and

Sensitivity to Change in the Physical Activity in Inpatient Rehabilitation Assessment', *Archives of Physical Medicine and Rehabilitation*, 92(12), pp. 2012–2017. doi:10.1016/j.apmr.2011.06.032.

Dixit, D., Spreadbury, J., Orlando, R., Hayward, E. and Kipps, C. (2020) 'Quality of Life Assessments in Individuals With Young-Onset Dementia and Their Caregivers', *Journal of Geriatric Psychiatry and Neurology*, p. 089198872093334. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0891988720933348>.

Dost, F.S., Ates Bulut, E., Dokuzlar, O., Kaya, D., Mutlay, F., Yesil Gurel, B.H. and Isik, A.T. (2022) 'Sarcopenia is as common in older patients with dementia with Lewy bodies as it is in those with Alzheimer's disease', *Geriatrics & Gerontology International*, 22(5), pp. 418–424. doi:10.1111/ggi.14383.

Draper, B. and Withall, A. (2016) 'Young onset dementia', *Internal Medicine Journal*, 46(7), pp. 779–786. doi:10.1111/imj.13099.

Drummond, G. and Vowler, S. (2011) 'Show the data, don't conceal them', *British Journal of Pharmacology*, 163(2), pp. 208–210. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1476-5381.2011.01251.x>.

Duong, S., Patel, T. and Chang, F. (2017) 'Dementia', *Canadian Pharmacists Journal / Revue des Pharmaciens du Canada*, 150(2), pp. 118–129. doi:10.1177/1715163517690745.

Eguchi, K., Hoshida, S., Ishikawa, J., Pickering, T.G., Schwartz, J.E., Shimada, K. and Kario, K. (2009) 'Nocturnal nondipping of heart rate predicts cardiovascular events in hypertensive patients', *Journal of Hypertension*, 27(11), pp. 2265–2270. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1097/hjh.0b013e328330a938>.

Emanuele RG Plini, Melnychuk, M.C., Andrews, R., Boyle, R.T., Whelan, R., Spence, J.S., Chapman, S.B., Robertson, I.H. and Dockree, P.M. (2023) 'Greater physical fitness (Vo2Max) in healthy older adults associated with increased integrity of the Locus Coeruleus-Noradrenergic system', *Research Square (Research Square)* [Preprint]. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-2556690/v2>.

Emanuele RG Plini, Melnychuk, M.C., Andrews, R., Boyle, R.T., Whelan, R., Spence, J.S., Chapman, S.B., Robertson, I.H. and Dockree, P.M. (2023) 'Greater physical fitness (Vo2Max) in healthy older adults associated with increased integrity of the Locus Coeruleus-Noradrenergic system', *Research Square (Research Square)* [Preprint]. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-2556690/v2>.

Erickson, K.I., Voss, M.W., Prakash, R.S., Basak, C., Szabo, A., Chaddock, L., Kim, J.S., Heo, S., Alves, H., White, S.M., Wojcicki, T.R., Mailey, E., Vieira, V.J., Martin, S.A., Pence, B.D., Woods, J.A., McAuley, E. and Kramer, A.F. (2011) 'Exercise training increases size of hippocampus and improves memory', *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 108(7), pp. 3017–3022. doi:10.1073/pnas.1015950108.

Field, M., Collins, M.W., Lovell, M.R. and Maroon, J. (2003) 'Does age play a role in recovery from sports-related concussion? A comparison of high school and collegiate athletes', *The Journal of Pediatrics*, 142(5), pp. 546–553. doi:10.1067/mpd.2003.190.

Fonseca, J.A., Costa-Pereira, A., Delgado, L., Silva, L.N., Magalhães, M., Castel-Branco, M.G. and Vaz, M. (2005) 'Pulmonary Function Electronic Monitoring Devices', *Chest*, 128(3), pp. 1258–1265. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1378/chest.128.3.1258>.

Fukutani, A. and Kurihara, T. (2015) 'Comparison of the muscle fascicle length between resistance-trained and untrained individuals: cross-sectional observation', SpringerPlus, 4(1). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40064-015-1133-1>.

Garg, P.K., Tan, A.X., Odden, M.C., Gardin, J.M., Lopez, O.L., Newman, A.B., Rawlings, A.M. and Mukamal, K.J. (2020) 'Brachial Flow-mediated Dilation and Risk of Dementia', *Alzheimer Disease & Associated Disorders*, 34(3), pp. 272–274. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1097/wad.0000000000000394>.

Garrido-Chamorro, R., Sirvent-Belando, J.E., González-Lorenzo, M., Blasco-Lafarga, C. and Roche, E. (2012) 'Skinfold Sum: Reference Values for Top Athletes', *International Journal of Morphology*, 30(3), pp. 803–809. doi:<https://doi.org/10.4067/s0717-95022012000300005>.

Gholamnezhad, Z., Boskabady, M.H. and Jahangiri, Z. (2020) 'Exercise and Dementia', *Physical Exercise for Human Health*, 1228, pp. 303–315. doi:10.1007/978-981-15-1792-1_20.

Gibson, G.E., Hirsch, J.A., Fonzetti, P., Jordon, B.D., Cirio, R.T. and Elder, J. (2016) 'Vitamin B1 (thiamine) and dementia', *Annals of the New York Academy of Sciences*, 1367(1), pp. 21–30. doi:10.1111/nyas.13031.

Graff-Radford, N.R. (2011) 'Can aerobic exercise protect against dementia?', *Alzheimer's Research & Therapy*, 3(1), p. 6. doi:10.1186/alzrt65.

Graham, N.S. and Sharp, D.J. (2019) 'Understanding neurodegeneration after traumatic brain injury: from mechanisms to clinical trials in dementia', *Journal of Neurology, Neurosurgery & Psychiatry*, 90(11), pp. 1221–1233. doi:10.1136/jnnp-2017-317557.

Greeta , A., Jamaiyah, H., Safiza, M., Khor, G., Kee, C., Ahmad, A., Suzana, S., Rahmah, R. and Faudzi, F. (2009) *Reliability, Technical Error of Measurements and Validity of Instruments for Nutritional Status Assessment of Adults in Malaysia*, *Singapore medical journal*. Available at: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/19907894/>.

Groot, C., Hooghiemstra, A.M., Raijmakers, P.G.H.M., van Berckel, B.N.M., Scheltens, P., Scherder, E.J.A., van der Flier, W.M. and Ossenkoppele, R. (2016) 'The effect of physical activity on cognitive function in patients with dementia: A meta-analysis of randomized control trials', *Ageing Research Reviews*, 25, pp. 13–23. doi:10.1016/j.arr.2015.11.005.

Handley, M., Bunn, F. and Goodman, C. (2017) 'Dementia-friendly interventions to improve the care of people living with dementia admitted to hospitals: a realist review', *BMJ Open*, 7(7), p. e015257. doi:10.1136/bmjopen-2016-015257.

Hartman, Y.A.W., Karssemeijer, E.G.A., van Diepen, L.A.M., Olde Rikkert, M.G.M. and Thijssen, D.H.J. (2018) 'Dementia Patients Are More Sedentary and Less Physically Active than Age- and Sex-Matched Cognitively Healthy Older Adults', *Dementia and Geriatric Cognitive Disorders*, 46(1-2), pp. 81–89. doi:10.1159/000491995.

Harvey, R.J., Skelton-Robinson, M. and Rossor, M. (2003) 'The prevalence and causes of dementia in people under the age of 65 years', *Journal of Neurology, Neurosurgery & Psychiatry*, 74(9), pp. 1206–1209. doi:10.1136/jnnp.74.9.1206.

Heath, C.A., Mercer, S.W. and Guthrie, B. (2014) 'Vascular comorbidities in younger people with dementia: a cross-sectional population-based study of 616 245 middle-aged

people in Scotland’, *Journal of Neurology, Neurosurgery & Psychiatry*, 86(9), pp. 959–964. doi:10.1136/jnnp-2014-309033.

Hendriks, S., Peetoom, K., Bakker, C., Koopmans, R., van der Flier, W., Papma, J., Verhey, F., de Vugt, M. and Köhler, S. (2022) ‘Global incidence of young-onset dementia: A systematic review and meta-analysis’, *Alzheimer’s & Dementia* [Preprint]. doi:10.1002/alz.12695.

Hendriks, S., Peetoom, K., Bakker, C., van der Flier, W.M., Papma, J.M., Koopmans, R., Verhey, F.R.J., de Vugt, M., Köhler, S., Withall, A., Parlevliet, J.L., Uysal-Bozkir, Ö., Gibson, R.C., Neita, S.M., Nielsen, T.R., Salem, L.C., Nyberg, J., Lopes, M.A., Dominguez, J.C. and De Guzman, M.F. (2021) ‘Global Prevalence of Young-Onset Dementia’, *JAMA Neurology*, 78(9). doi:10.1001/jamaneurol.2021.2161.

Hernandez, G., Garin, O., Dima, A.L., Pont, A., Martí Pastor, M., Alonso, J., Van Ganse, E., Laforest, L., de Bruin, M., Mayoral, K., Serra-Sutton, V. and Ferrer, M. (2019) ‘EuroQol (EQ-5D-5L) Validity in Assessing the Quality of Life in Adults With Asthma: Cross-Sectional Study’, *Journal of Medical Internet Research*, 21(1), p. e10178. doi:https://doi.org/10.2196/10178.

Hewitt, P., Watts, C., Hussey, J., Power, K. and Williams, T. (2013) ‘Does a Structured Gardening Programme Improve Well-Being in Young-Onset Dementia? A Preliminary Study’, *British Journal of Occupational Therapy*, 76(8), pp. 355–361. doi:10.4276/030802213x13757040168270.

Heyn, P., Abreu, B. and Ottenbacher, K. (2004) ‘From the School of Allied Health Sciences, Division of Rehabilitation Sciences (Heyn’, *Abreu, Ottenbacher) and Sealy Center on Aging*, 85(10). doi:10.1016/j.apmr.2004.03.019.

HILDEBRAND, M., VAN HEES, V.T., HANSEN, B.H. and EKELUND, U. (2014) ‘Age Group Comparability of Raw Accelerometer Output from Wrist- and Hip-Worn Monitors’, *Medicine & Science in Sports & Exercise*, 46(9), pp. 1816–1824. doi:https://doi.org/10.1249/mss.0000000000000289.

Hildebrand, M., van Hees, V.T., Hansen, B.H., & Ekelund, U. (2014). Age group comparability of raw accelerometer output from wrist- and

Hillman, C.H., Snook, E.M. and Jerome, G.J. (2003) ‘Acute cardiovascular exercise and executive control function’, *International Journal of Psychophysiology*, 48(3), pp. 307–314. doi:10.1016/s0167-8760(03)00080-1.

Hölscher, C. (1998) ‘Possible Causes of Alzheimer’s Disease: Amyloid Fragments, Free Radicals, and Calcium Homeostasis’, *Neurobiology of Disease*, 5(3), pp. 129–141. doi:10.1006/nbdi.1998.0193.

Holthoff, V.A., Marschner, K., Scharf, M., Steding, J., Meyer, S., Koch, R. and Donix, M. (2015) ‘Effects of Physical Activity Training in Patients with Alzheimer’s Dementia: Results of a Pilot RCT Study’, *PLOS ONE*. Edited by T.J. Quinn, 10(4), p. e0121478. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0121478.

Hommet, C., Mondon, K., Camus, V., De Toffol, B. and Constans, T. (2008) ‘Epilepsy and Dementia in the Elderly’, *Dementia and Geriatric Cognitive Disorders*, 25(4), pp. 293–300. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1159/000119103>.

Hong, S.-G., Kim, J.-H. and Jun, T.-W. (2018) ‘Effects of 12-Week Resistance Exercise on Electroencephalogram Patterns and Cognitive Function in the Elderly With Mild Cognitive Impairment’, *Clinical Journal of Sport Medicine*, 28(6), pp. 500–508. doi:10.1097/jsm.0000000000000476.

Hughes, T.M., Wagenknecht, L.E., Craft, S., Mintz, A., Heiss, G., Palta, P., Wong, D., Zhou, Y., Knopman, D., Mosley, T.H. and Gottesman, R.F. (2018) ‘Arterial stiffness and dementia pathology’, *Neurology*, 90(14), pp. e1248–e1256. doi:10.1212/WNL.00000000000005259.

Hurlbert, S.H., Levine, R.A. and Utts, J. (2019) ‘Coup de Grâce for a Tough Old Bull: “Statistically Significant” Expires’, *The American Statistician*, 73(sup1), pp. 352–357. doi:https://doi.org/10.1080/00031305.2018.1543616.

Jürgen Bortz, Christof Schuster and Springer-Verlag Gmbh (2013) *Statistik für Human- und Sozialwissenschaftler : limitierte Sonderausgabe : mit 70 Abbildungen und 163 Tabellen*. Berlin: Springer.

Karssemeijer, E.G.A. (Esther), Aaronson, J.A. (Justine), Bossers, W.J. (Willem), Smits, T. (Tara), Olde Rikkert, M.G.M. (Marcel) and Kessels, R.P.C. (Roy) (2017) ‘Positive effects

of combined cognitive and physical exercise training on cognitive function in older adults with mild cognitive impairment or dementia: A meta-analysis', *Ageing Research Reviews*, 40, pp. 75–83. doi:10.1016/j.arr.2017.09.003.

Keller, K. and Engelhardt, M. (2014) 'Strength and muscle mass loss with aging process. Age and strength loss', *Muscles, ligaments and tendons journal*, 3(4), pp. 346–50. Available at: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC3940510/>.

Kelley, B.J., Boeve, B.F. and Josephs, K.A. (2008) 'Young-Onset Dementia', *Archives of Neurology*, 65(11), p. 1502. doi:10.1001/archneur.65.11.1502.

Kilty, C., Cahill, S., Foley, T. and Fox, S. (2022) 'Young onset dementia: implications for employment and finances', *Dementia*, p. 147130122211323. doi:10.1177/14713012221132374.

Kim, J., Lee, H., Park, S.K., Park, J.-H., Jeong, H.-R., Lee, S., Lee, H., Seol, E. and Hoe, H.-S. (2021) 'Donepezil Regulates LPS and A β -Stimulated Neuroinflammation through MAPK/NLRP3 Inflammasome/STAT3 Signaling', *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, 22(19), p. 10637. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms221910637>.

Knopman, D., Boland, L.L., Mosley, T., Howard, G., Liao, D., Szklo, M., McGovern, P. and Folsom, A.R. (2001) 'Cardiovascular risk factors and cognitive decline in middle-aged adults', *Neurology*, 56(1), pp. 42–48. doi:10.1212/wnl.56.1.42.

Kodama, S. (2009) 'Cardiorespiratory Fitness as a Quantitative Predictor of All-Cause Mortality and Cardiovascular Events in Healthy Men and Women', *JAMA*, 301(19), p. 2024. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.2009.681>.

Koedam, E.L.G.E., Lauffer, V., van der Vlies, A.E., van der Flier, W.M., Scheltens, P. and Pijnenburg, Y.A.L. (2010) 'Early-Versus Late-Onset Alzheimer's Disease: More than Age Alone', *Journal of Alzheimer's Disease*, 19(4), pp. 1401–1408. doi:10.3233/jad-2010-1337.

Kokjohn, T.A. and Roher, A.E. (2009) 'Amyloid precursor protein transgenic mouse models and Alzheimer's disease: Understanding the paradigms, limitations, and contributions', *Alzheimer's & Dementia*, 5(4), pp. 340–347. doi:10.1016/j.jalz.2009.03.002.

Kolanowski, A.M. and Garr, M. (1999) 'The Relation of Premorbid Factors to Aggressive Physical Behavior in Dementia', *Journal of Neuroscience Nursing*, 31(5), pp. 278–284. doi:10.1097/01376517-199910000-00004.

Koopmans, R. and Rosness, T. (2014) 'Young onset dementia – what does the name imply?', *International Psychogeriatrics*, 26(12), pp. 1931–1933. doi:10.1017/s1041610214001574.

Kübra Nur Menengiç, Uğur Ovacık, Feray Güngör, Cinar, N. and İpek Yeldan (2023) 'Comparison of manual dexterity of people with Alzheimer's disease and cognitively healthy older adults: The impact of cognition', 19(S4). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1002/alz.064919>.

Kumar, S.N.S., Omar, B., Htwe, O., Joseph, L.H., Krishnan, J., Esfehiani, A.J. and Min, L.L. (2014) 'Reliability, agreement, and validity of digital weighing scale with MatScan in limb load measurement', *Journal of Rehabilitation Research and Development*, 51(4), pp. 591–598. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1682/jrrd.2013.07.0166>.

Kuruppu, D. and Matthews, B. (2013) 'Young-Onset Dementia', *Seminars in Neurology*, 33(04), pp. 365–385. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1055/s-0033-1359320>.

Ladecola, C. (2014) 'Hypertension and Dementia', *Hypertension*, 64(1), pp. 3–5. doi:10.1161/hypertensionaha.114.03040.

Lakens, D. (2013) 'Calculating and reporting effect sizes to facilitate cumulative science: a practical primer for t-tests and ANOVAs', *Frontiers in Psychology*, 4(863). doi:<https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2013.00863>.

Lamb, S.E., Sheehan, B., Atherton, N., Nichols, V., Collins, H., Mistry, D., Dosanjh, S., Slowther, A.M., Khan, I., Petrou, S. and Lall, R. (2018) 'Dementia And Physical Activity (DAPA) trial of moderate to high intensity exercise training for people with dementia: randomised controlled trial', *BMJ*, 361, p. k1675. doi:10.1136/bmj.k1675.

Langa, K.M. (2018) *Cognitive Aging, Dementia, and the Future of an Aging Population*, Nih.gov. National Academies Press (US). Available at: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK513075/>.

Law, C.-K., Lam, F.M., Chung, R.C. and Pang, M.Y. (2020) 'Physical exercise attenuates cognitive decline and reduces behavioural problems in people with mild cognitive impairment and dementia: a systematic review', *Journal of physiotherapy*, 66(1), pp. 9–18. doi:10.1016/j.jphys.2019.11.014.

Lee, A.Y. (2011) 'Vascular Dementia', *Chonnam Medical Journal*, 47(2), p. 66. doi:10.4068/cmj.2011.47.2.66.

Lennon, O.C., Denis, R.S., Grace, N. and Blake, C. (2011) 'Feasibility, criterion validity and retest reliability of exercise testing using the Astrand-rhyming test protocol with an adaptive ergometer in stroke patients', *Disability and Rehabilitation*, 34(14), pp. 1149–1156. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3109/09638288.2011.635748>.

Li, Y., Li, Y., Li, X., Zhang, S., Zhao, J., Zhu, X. and Tian, G. (2017) 'Head Injury as a Risk Factor for Dementia and Alzheimer's Disease: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis of 32 Observational Studies', *PLOS ONE*. Edited by J. Lifshitz, 12(1), p. e0169650. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0169650.

Liguori, G. and American (2020) *ACSM's Guidelines for Exercise Testing and Prescription*. Lippincott Williams & Wilkins.

Lim, H.M., Chia, Y.C., Ching, S.M. and Chinna, K. (2019) 'Number of blood pressure measurements needed to estimate long-term visit-to-visit systolic blood pressure variability for predicting cardiovascular risk: a 10-year retrospective cohort study in a primary care clinic in Malaysia', *BMJ Open*, 9(4), p. e025322. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2018-025322>.

Lindstrom-Hazel, D.K. and VanderVlies Veenstra, N. (2015) 'Examining the Purdue Pegboard Test for Occupational Therapy Practice', *The Open Journal of Occupational Therapy*, 3(3). doi:<https://doi.org/10.15453/2168-6408.1178>.

Long, A., Di Lorito, C., Logan, P., Booth, V., Howe, L., Hood-Moore, V. and van der Wardt, V. (2020) 'The Impact of a Dementia-Friendly Exercise Class on People Living with Dementia: A Mixed-Methods Study', *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 17(12), p. 4562. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17124562>.

Löve, J., Moore, C.D. and Hensing, G. (2011) 'Validation of the Swedish translation of the general self-efficacy scale', *Quality of Life Research*, 21(7), pp. 1249–1253. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1007/s11136-011-0030-5>.

Mackenzie, I.R.A. and Neumann, M. (2016) 'Molecular neuropathology of frontotemporal dementia: insights into disease mechanisms from postmortem studies', *Journal of Neurochemistry*, 138(S1), pp. 54–70. doi:10.1111/jnc.13588.

Masellis, M., Sherborn, K., Neto, P., Sadovnick, D.A., Hsiung, G.-Y.R., Black, S.E., Prasad, S., Williams, M. and Gauthier, S. (2013) 'Early-onset dementias: diagnostic and etiological considerations', *Alzheimer's Research & Therapy*, 5(Suppl 1), p. S7. doi:10.1186/alzrt197.

Mckee, A.C. and Daneshvar, D.H. (2015) 'The neuropathology of traumatic brain injury', *Handbook of Clinical Neurology*, 127(1), pp. 45–66. doi:10.1016/b978-0-444-52892-6.00004-0.

Middleton, J., Tran, Y. and Craig, A. (2007) 'Relationship Between Quality of Life and Self-Efficacy in Persons With Spinal Cord Injuries', *Archives of Physical Medicine and Rehabilitation*, 88(12), pp. 1643–1648. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apmr.2007.09.001>.

Migueles, J.H., Cadenas-Sanchez, C., Ekelund, U., Delisle Nyström, C., Mora-Gonzalez, J., Löf, M., Labayen, I., Ruiz, J.R. and Ortega, F.B. (2017) 'Accelerometer Data Collection and Processing Criteria to Assess Physical Activity and Other Outcomes: A Systematic Review and Practical Considerations', *Sports Medicine*, 47(9), pp. 1821–1845. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1007/s40279-017-0716-0>.

Migueles, J.H., Rowlands, A.V., Huber, F., Sabia, S., & Hees, V.T. (2019). GGIR: A research community-driven open source R package for generating physical activity and sleep outcomes from multi-day raw accelerometer data. *Journal for the Measurement of Physical Behaviour*, 2(3), 188–196. <https://doi.org/10.1123/jmpb.2018-0063>.

Millenaar, J.K., Bakker, C., Koopmans, R.T.C.M., Verhey, F.R.J., Kurz, A. and de Vugt, M.E. (2016) 'The care needs and experiences with the use of services of people with young-

onset dementia and their caregivers: a systematic review’, *International Journal of Geriatric Psychiatry*, 31(12), pp. 1261–1276. doi:10.1002/gps.4502.

Miller, M., Hankinson, J., Brusasco, V., Burgos, F., Casaburi, R., Coates, A., Crapo, R., Enright, P., Van Der Grinten, C., Gustafsson, P., Jensen, R., Johnson, D., Macintyre, N., McKay, R., Navajas, D., Pedersen, O., Pellegrino, R., Viegi, G. and Wanger, J. (2005) ‘SERIES ““ATS/ERS TASK FORCE: STANDARDISATION OF LUNG FUNCTION TESTING”” Standardisation of spirometry’, *Eur Respir J*, 26(2), pp. 319–338. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1183/09031936.05.00034805>.

Mohandas, E., Rajmohan, V. and Raghunath, B. (2009) ‘Neurobiology of Alzheimer’s disease’, *Indian Journal of Psychiatry*, 51(1), p. 55. doi:10.4103/0019-5545.44908.

Moore, G.E., J Larry Durstine, Patricia Lynn Painter and American (2016) *ACSM’s exercise management for persons with chronic diseases and disabilities*. Champaign, IL: Human Kinetics.

Morris, G.P., Clark, I.A. and Vissel, B. (2014) ‘Inconsistencies and Controversies Surrounding the Amyloid Hypothesis of Alzheimer’s Disease’, *Acta Neuropathologica Communications*, 2(1). doi:10.1186/s40478-014-0135-5.

Mosconi, L. (2013) ‘Glucose metabolism in normal aging and Alzheimer’s disease: methodological and physiological considerations for PET studies’, *Clinical and Translational Imaging*, 1(4), pp. 217–233. doi:10.1007/s40336-013-0026-y.

Moussa, C., Hebron, M., Huang, X., Ahn, J., Rissman, R.A., Aisen, P.S. and Turner, R.S. (2017) ‘Resveratrol regulates neuro-inflammation and induces adaptive immunity in Alzheimer’s disease’, *Journal of Neuroinflammation*, 14(1). doi:10.1186/s12974-016-0779-0.

Mpampoulis, T., Methenitis, S., Papadopoulos, C., Papadimas, G., Spiliopoulou, P., Stasinaki, A.-N., Bogdanis, G.C., Karampatsos, G. and Terzis, G. (2021) ‘Weak Association between Vastus Lateralis Muscle Fiber Composition and Fascicle Length in Young Untrained Females’, *Sports*, 9(5), p. 56. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3390/sports9050056>.

Nanda, B., Balde, J. and Manjunatha, S. (2013) 'The Acute Effects of a Single Bout of Moderate-intensity Aerobic Exercise on Cognitive Functions in Healthy Adult Males', *JOURNAL OF CLINICAL AND DIAGNOSTIC RESEARCH*, 7(9). doi:10.7860/jcdr/2013/5855.3341.

Narici, M., McPhee, J., Conte, M., Franchi, M.V., Mitchell, K., Tagliaferri, S., Monti, E., Marcolin, G., Atherton, P.J., Smith, K., Phillips, B., Lund, J., Franceschi, C., Maggio, M. and Butler-Browne, G.S. (2021) 'Age-related alterations in muscle architecture are a signature of sarcopenia: the ultrasound sarcopenia index', *Journal of Cachexia, Sarcopenia and Muscle* [Preprint]. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1002/jcsm.12720>.

Neary, D., Snowden, J.S., Gustafson, L., Passant, U., Stuss, D., Black, S., Freedman, M., Kertesz, A., Robert, P.H., Albert, M., Boone, K., Miller, B.L., Cummings, J. and Benson, D.F. (1998) 'Frontotemporal lobar degeneration: a consensus on clinical diagnostic criteria', *Neurology*, 51(6), pp. 1546–54. doi:10.1212/wnl.51.6.1546.

Nichols (2022) 'Estimation of the global prevalence of dementia in 2019 and forecasted prevalence in 2050: an analysis for the Global Burden of Disease Study 2019', *The Lancet Public Health*, 7(2). doi:10.1016/s2468-2667(21)00249-8.

Nordgren, B., Fridén, C., Jansson, E., Österlund, T., Grooten, W.J., Opava, C.H. and Rickenlund, A. (2014) 'Criterion validation of two submaximal aerobic fitness tests, the self-monitoring Fox-walk test and the Åstrand cycle test in people with rheumatoid arthritis', *BMC Musculoskeletal Disorders*, 15(1). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2474-15-305>.

Nordström, P., Nordström, A., Eriksson, M., Wahlund, L.-O. and Gustafson, Y. (2013) 'Risk Factors in Late Adolescence for Young-Onset Dementia in Men', *JAMA Internal Medicine*, 173(17), p. 1612. doi:10.1001/jamainternmed.2013.9079.

Novek, S., Shoostari, S. and Menec, V.H. (2016) 'Comparing the Overall Health, Stress, and Characteristics of Canadians with Early-Onset and Late-Onset Dementia', *Journal of Aging and Health*, 28(6), pp. 1016–1037. doi:10.1177/0898264315615575.

O'Brien, J.T. and Thomas, A. (2015) 'Vascular dementia', *The Lancet*, 386(10004), pp. 1698–1706. doi:10.1016/s0140-6736(15)00463-8.

O'Malley, M., Carter, J., Stamou, V., LaFontaine, J., Oyeboode, J. and Parkes, J. (2019) 'Receiving a diagnosis of young onset dementia: a scoping review of lived experiences', *Aging & Mental Health*, 25(1), pp. 1–12. doi:10.1080/13607863.2019.1673699.

Onyike, C.U. and Diehl-Schmid, J. (2013) 'The epidemiology of frontotemporal dementia', *International review of psychiatry (Abingdon, England)*, 25(2), pp. 130–7. doi:10.3109/09540261.2013.776523.

Owens, L., Bracewell, J., Benedetto, A., Dawson, N., Gaffney, C. and Parkin, E. (2022) 'BACE1 Overexpression Reduces SH-SY5Y Cell Viability Through a Mechanism Distinct from Amyloid- β Peptide Accumulation: Beta Prime-Mediated Competitive Depletion of sA β PP α ', *Journal of Alzheimer's Disease*, pp. 1–20. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3233/jad-215457>.

Owens, L.V., Benedetto, A., Dawson, N., Gaffney, C.J. and Parkin, E.T. (2021) 'Gene therapy-mediated enhancement of protective protein expression for the treatment of Alzheimer's disease', *Brain Research*, 1753, p. 147264. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.brainres.2020.147264>.

Pandis, D. and Scarmeas, N. (2012) 'Seizures in Alzheimer Disease: Clinical and Epidemiological Data', *Epilepsy Currents*, 12(5), pp. 184–187. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5698/1535-7511-12.5.184>.

Panegyres, P.K. and Frencham, K. (2007) 'Course and Causes of Suspected Dementia in Young Adults: A Longitudinal Study', *American Journal of Alzheimer's Disease & Other Dementias*®, 22(1), pp. 48–56. doi:10.1177/1533317506295887.

Park, J.H., Moon, J.H., Kim, H.J., Kong, M.H. and Oh, Y.H. (2020) 'Sedentary lifestyle: Overview of Updated Evidence of Potential Health Risks', *Korean Journal of Family Medicine*, 41(6), pp. 365–373. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.4082/kjfm.20.0165>.

Parry, S., Chow, M., Batchelor, F. and Fary, R.E. (2018) 'Physical activity and sedentary behaviour in a residential aged care facility', *Australasian Journal on Ageing*, 38(1), pp. E12–E18. doi:10.1111/ajag.12589.

Pedroza, P., Chakrabarti, S., Chapin, A., Liu, A., Matyasz, T. and Dieleman, J.L. (2019) 'COSTS OF ALZHEIMER'S DISEASE AND DEMENTIA IN 188 COUNTRIES', *Alzheimer's & Dementia*, 15(7), p. P1635. doi:10.1016/j.jalz.2019.06.4877.

Potts, C., Richardson, J., Bond, R.B., Price, R.K., Mulvenna, M.D., Zvolsky, P., Harvey, M., Hughes, C.F. and Duffy, F. (2021) 'Reliability of Addenbrooke's Cognitive Examination III in Differentiating between dementia, Mild Cognitive Impairment and Older Adults Who Have Not Reported Cognitive Problems', *European Journal of Ageing*, 19(3). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10433-021-00652-4>.

Rimmer, J. and Smith, D. (2009) *ACSM's exercise management for persons with chronic diseases and disabilities*. 3rd edn. Edited by L. Dustin, G. Moore, P. Painter, and S. Roberts. Human Kinetics, pp. 368–374.

Rizzi, L., Rosset, I. and Roriz-Cruz, M. (2014) 'Global Epidemiology of Dementia: Alzheimer's and Vascular Types', *BioMed Research International*, 2014, pp. 1–8. doi:10.1155/2014/908915.

Spitzer, S., Kessler, R.C., Williams, J.B. and First, M.B. (2006) *A Brief Measure for Assessing Generalized Anxiety Disorder: The GAD-7*, *Archives of internal medicine*. Available at: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/16717171/>.

Roberts, H.C., Denison, H.J., Martin, H.J., Patel, H.P., Syddall, H., Cooper, C. and Sayer, A.A. (2011) 'A review of the measurement of grip strength in clinical and epidemiological studies: towards a standardised approach', *Age and Ageing*, 40(4), pp. 423–429. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1093/ageing/afr051>.

Rodgers, C., Rogerson, D., Stevenson, J. and Porock, D. (2018) 'Physical activity for people with young-onset dementia and carers: protocol for a scoping review', *Systematic Reviews*, 7(1). doi:10.1186/s13643-018-0698-5.

Rodgers, J.L., Jones, J., Bolleddu, S.I., Vanthenapalli, S., Rodgers, L.E., Shah, K., Karia, K. and Panguluri, S.K. (2019) 'Cardiovascular Risks Associated with Gender and Aging', *Journal of Cardiovascular Development and Disease*, 6(2), p. 19. doi:10.3390/jcdd6020019.

Rohrer, J.D. and Warren, J.D. (2011) 'Phenotypic signatures of genetic frontotemporal dementia', *Current Opinion in Neurology*, 24(6), pp. 542–549. doi:10.1097/wco.0b013e32834cd442.

Rohrer, J.D., Guerreiro, R., Vandrovcova, J., Uphill, J., Reiman, D., Beck, J., Isaacs, A.M., Authier, A., Ferrari, R., Fox, N.C., Mackenzie, I.R.A., Warren, J.D., de Silva, R., Holton, J., Revesz, T., Hardy, J., Mead, S. and Rossor, M.N. (2009) 'The heritability and genetics of frontotemporal lobar degeneration', *Neurology*, 73(18), pp. 1451–1456. doi:10.1212/wnl.0b013e3181bf997a.

Roman de Mettelinge, T., Calders, P. and Cambier, D. (2021) 'The Effects of Aerobic Exercise in Patients with Early-Onset Dementia: A Scoping Review', *Dementia and Geriatric Cognitive Disorders*, 50(1), pp. 1–8. doi:10.1159/000516231.

Rossor, M.N., Fox, N.C., Mummery, C.J., Schott, J.M. and Warren, J.D. (2010) 'The diagnosis of young-onset dementia', *Lancet neurology*, 9(8), pp. 793–806. doi:10.1016/S1474-4422(10)70159-9.

S., Jensen, C., Portelius, E., Siersma, V., Høgh, P., Wermuth, L., Blennow, K., Zetterberg, H., Waldemar, G., Gregers Hasselbalch, S. and Hviid Simonsen, A. (2016) 'Cerebrospinal Fluid Amyloid Beta and Tau Concentrations Are Not Modulated by 16 Weeks of Moderate-to High-Intensity Physical Exercise in Patients with Alzheimer Disease', *Dementia and Geriatric Cognitive Disorders*, 42(3-4), pp. 146–158. doi:10.1159/000449408.

Salisbury, D., Mathiason, M.A. and Yu, F. (2021) 'Exercise Dose and Aerobic Fitness Response in Alzheimer's Dementia in the FIT-AD Trial', *International Journal of Sports Medicine*, 43(10). doi:10.1055/a-1639-2307.

Sampaio, A., Marques-Aleixo, I., Seabra, A., Mota, J. and Carvalho, J. (2021) 'Physical exercise for individuals with dementia: potential benefits perceived by formal caregivers', *BMC Geriatrics*, 21(1). doi:10.1186/s12877-020-01938-5.

Sampson, E.L., Warren, J. and Rossor, M. (2004) 'Young onset dementia', *Postgraduate Medical Journal*, 80(941), pp. 125–139. doi:10.1136/pgmj.2003.011171.

Sato, K., Ogoh, S., Hirasawa, A., Oue, A. and Sadamoto, T. (2011) 'The distribution of blood flow in the carotid and vertebral arteries during dynamic exercise in humans', *The Journal of Physiology*, 589(11), pp. 2847–2856. doi:10.1113/jphysiol.2010.204461.

Seaquist, E.R. (2009) 'The Final Frontier: How Does Diabetes Affect the Brain?', *Diabetes*, 59(1), pp. 4–5. doi:10.2337/db09-1600.

Seelaar, H., Rohrer, J.D., Pijnenburg, Y.A.L., Fox, N.C. and van Swieten, J.C. (2010) 'Clinical, genetic and pathological heterogeneity of frontotemporal dementia: a review', *Journal of Neurology, Neurosurgery & Psychiatry*, 82(5), pp. 476–486. doi:10.1136/jnnp.2010.212225.

Seeley, W.W., Crawford, R.K., Zhou, J., Miller, B.L. and Greicius, M.D. (2009) 'Neurodegenerative Diseases Target Large-Scale Human Brain Networks', *Neuron*, 62(1), pp. 42–52. doi:10.1016/j.neuron.2009.03.024.

Semple, B.D., Blomgren, K., Gimlin, K., Ferriero, D.M. and Noble-Haeusslein, L.J. (2013) 'Brain development in rodents and humans: Identifying benchmarks of maturation and vulnerability to injury across species', *Progress in Neurobiology*, 106-107(1-16), pp. 1–16. doi:10.1016/j.pneurobio.2013.04.001.

Siddappaji, K.K. and Gopal, S. (2021) 'Molecular mechanisms in Alzheimer's disease and the impact of physical exercise with advancements in therapeutic approaches', *AIMS Neuroscience*, 8(3), pp. 357–389. doi:10.3934/neuroscience.2021020.

Sleiman, S.F., Henry, J., Al-Haddad, R., El Hayek, L., Abou Haidar, E., Stringer, T., Ulja, D., Karuppagounder, S.S., Holson, E.B., Ratan, R.R., Ninan, I. and Chao, M.V. (2016) 'Exercise promotes the expression of brain derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF) through the action of the ketone body β -hydroxybutyrate', *eLife*, 5(2). doi:10.7554/elife.15092.

Sobol, N.A., Hoffmann, K., Frederiksen, K.S., Vogel, A., Vestergaard, K., Braendgaard, H., Gottrup, H., Lolk, A., Wermuth, L., Jakobsen, S., Laugesen, L., Gergelyffy, R., Høgh, P., Bjerregaard, E., Siersma, V., Andersen, B.B., Johannsen, P., Waldemar, G., Hasselbalch, S.G. and Beyer, N. (2016) 'Effect of aerobic exercise on physical performance in patients with Alzheimer's disease', *Alzheimer's & Dementia*, 12(12), pp. 1207–1215. doi:10.1016/j.jalz.2016.05.004.

Stillman, C.M., Cohen, J., Lehman, M.E. and Erickson, K.I. (2016) 'Mediators of Physical Activity on Neurocognitive Function: A Review at Multiple Levels of Analysis', *Frontiers in Human Neuroscience*, 10. doi:10.3389/fnhum.2016.00626.

Sun, Y., Fu, Z., Bo, Q., Mao, Z., Ma, X. and Wang, C. (2020) 'The reliability and validity of PHQ-9 in patients with major depressive disorder in psychiatric hospital', *BMC Psychiatry*, 20(1), p. 474. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12888-020-02885-6>.

Tachibana, H., Washida, K., Kowa, H., Kanda, F. and Toda, T. (2016) 'Vascular Function in Alzheimer's Disease and Vascular Dementia', *American Journal of Alzheimer's Disease & Other Dementiasr*, 31(5), pp. 437–442. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1533317516653820>.

Takenoshita, S., Terada, S., Yoshida, H., Yamaguchi, M., Yabe, M., Imai, N., Horiuchi, M., Miki, T., Yokota, O. and Yamada, N. (2019) 'Validation of Addenbrooke's cognitive examination III for detecting mild cognitive impairment and dementia in Japan', *BMC Geriatrics*, 19(1). doi:<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12877-019-1120-4>.

Tan, Z.-X., Dong, F., Wu, L.-Y., Feng, Y.-S. and Zhang, F. (2021) 'The Beneficial Role of Exercise on Treating Alzheimer's Disease by Inhibiting β -Amyloid Peptide', *Molecular Neurobiology*, 58(11), pp. 5890–5906. doi:10.1007/s12035-021-02514-7.

Thomas, R., Zimmerman, S.D., Yuede, K.M., Cirrito, J.R., Tai, L.M., Timson, B.F. and Yuede, C.M. (2020) 'Exercise Training Results in Lower Amyloid Plaque Load and Greater Cognitive Function in an Intensity Dependent Manner in the Tg2576 Mouse Model of Alzheimer's Disease', *Brain Sciences*, 10(2), p. 88. doi:10.3390/brainsci10020088.

Ticinesi, A., Narici, M.V., Lauretani, F., Nouvenne, A., Colizzi, E., Mantovani, M., Corsonello, A., Landi, F., Meschi, T. and Maggio, M. (2018) 'Assessing sarcopenia with vastus lateralis muscle ultrasound: an operative protocol', *Aging Clinical and Experimental Research*, 30(12), pp. 1437–1443. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1007/s40520-018-0958-1>.

Tolhurst, E., Bhattacharyya, S. and Kingston, P. (2012) 'Young onset dementia: The impact of emergent age-based factors upon personhood', *Dementia*, 13(2), pp. 193–206. doi:10.1177/1471301212456278.

Tonga, J.B., Eilertsen, D.-E., Solem, I.K.L., Arnevik, E.A., Korsnes, M.S. and Ulstein, I.D. (2020) 'Effect of Self-Efficacy on Quality of Life in People With Mild Cognitive Impairment and Mild Dementia: The Mediating Roles of Depression and Anxiety', *American Journal of Alzheimer's Disease & Other Dementias*®, 35, p. 153331751988526. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1533317519885264>.

Toots, A., Littbrand, H., Boström, G., Hörnsten, C., Holmberg, H., Lundin-Olsson, L., Lindelöf, N., Nordström, P., Gustafson, Y. and Rosendahl, E. (2017) 'Effects of Exercise on Cognitive Function in Older People with Dementia: A Randomized Controlled Trial', *Journal of Alzheimer's Disease*, 60(1), pp. 323–332. doi:10.3233/jad-170014.

Trigiani, L.J. and Hamel, E. (2017) 'An endothelial link between the benefits of physical exercise in dementia', *Journal of Cerebral Blood Flow & Metabolism*, 37(8), pp. 2649–2664. doi:10.1177/0271678x17714655.

Trigiani, L.J. and Hamel, E. (2017) 'An endothelial link between the benefits of physical exercise in dementia', *Journal of Cerebral Blood Flow & Metabolism*, 37(8), pp. 2649–2664. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0271678x17714655>.

Tsao, C.W., Seshadri, S., Beiser, A.S., Westwood, A.J., DeCarli, C., Au, R., Himali, J.J., Hamburg, N.M., Vita, J.A., Levy, D., Larson, M.G., Benjamin, E.J., Wolf, P.A., Vasan, R.S. and Mitchell, G.F. (2013) 'Relations of arterial stiffness and endothelial function to brain aging in the community', *Neurology*, 81(11), pp. 984–991. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1212/wnl.0b013e3182a43e1c>.

Unger, T., Borghi, C., Charchar, F., Khan, N.A., Poulter, N.R., Prabhakaran, D., Ramirez, A., Schlaich, M., Stergiou, G.S., Tomaszewski, M., Wainford, R.D., Williams, B. and Schutte, A.E. (2020) '2020 International Society of Hypertension Global Hypertension Practice Guidelines', *Hypertension*, 75(6), pp. 1334–1357. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1161/hypertensionaha.120.15026>.

Väisänen, D., Ekblom, Ö., Ekblom-Bak, E., Andersson, E., Nilsson, J. and Ekblom, M. (2019) 'Criterion validity of the Ekblom-Bak and the Åstrand submaximal test in an elderly population', *European Journal of Applied Physiology*, 120(2), pp. 307–316. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00421-019-04275-7>.

Van de Pol, L.A., Hensel, A., Barkhof, F., Gertz, H.J., Scheltens, P. and van der Flier, W.M. (2006) 'Hippocampal atrophy in Alzheimer disease: Age matters', *Neurology*, 66(2), pp. 236–238. doi:10.1212/01.wnl.0000194240.47892.4d.

Van Hees, V.T., Fang, Z., Langford, J., Assah, F., Mohammad, A., da Silva, I.C.M., Trenell, M.I., White, T., Wareham, N.J., & Brage, S. (2014). Autocalibration of accelerometer data for free-living physical activity assessment using local gravity and temperature: An evaluation on four continents. *Journal of Applied Physiology*, 117(7), 738–744. <https://doi.org/10.1152/jappphysiol.00421.2014>

Van Hees, V.T., Gorzelniak, L., León, E.C.D., Eder, M., Pias, M., Taherian, S., Ekelund, U., Renström, F., Franks, P.W., Horsch, A., & Brage, S. (2013). Separating movement and gravity components in an acceleration signal and implications for the assessment of human daily physical activity. *PLoS One*, 8(4), Article 691. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0061691>

Van Hees, V.T., Sabia, S., Jones, S.E., Wood, A.R., Anderson, K.N., Kivimäki, M., Frayling, T.M., Pack, A.I., Bucan, M., Trenell, M.I., Mazzotti, D.R., Gehrman, P.R., Singh-Manoux, B.A., & Weedon, M.N. (2018). Estimating sleep parameters using an accelerometer without sleep diary. *Scientific Reports*, 8(1), Article 12975. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-018-31266-z>

Vidoni, E.D., Morris, J.K., Watts, A., Perry, M., Clutton, J., Van Sciver, A., Kamat, A.S., Mahnken, J., Hunt, S.L., Townley, R., Honea, R., Shaw, A.R., Johnson, D.K., Vacek, J. and Burns, J.M. (2021) 'Effect of aerobic exercise on amyloid accumulation in preclinical Alzheimer's: A 1-year randomized controlled trial', *PLOS ONE*. Edited by A.I. Bush, 16(1), p. e0244893. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0244893.

Vital, T.M., Hernández, S.S.S., Pedroso, R.V., Teixeira, C.V.L., Garuffi, M., Stein, A.M., Costa, J.L.R. and Stella, F. (2012) 'Effects of weight training on cognitive functions in elderly with Alzheimer's disease', *Dementia & Neuropsychologia*, 6(4), pp. 253–259. doi:10.1590/s1980-57642012dn06040009.

Vreugdenhil, A., Cannell, J., Davies, A. and Razay, G. (2012) 'A community-based exercise programme to improve functional ability in people with Alzheimer's disease: a

randomized controlled trial’, *Scandinavian journal of caring sciences*, 26(1), pp. 12–9. doi:10.1111/j.1471-6712.2011.00895.x.

Walston, J.D. (2012) ‘Sarcopenia in Older Adults’, *Current Opinion in Rheumatology*, 24(6), pp. 623–627. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1097/bor.0b013e328358d59b>.

Wang, A.Y., Leung, L.Y., Puttock, E.J., Luetmer, P.H., Kallmes, D.F., Nelson, J., Fu, S., Zheng, C., Liu, H., Chen, W. and Kent, D.M. (2022) ‘Stratifying Future Stroke Risk with Incidentally Discovered White Matter Disease Severity and Covert Brain Infarct Site’, *Cerebrovascular Diseases (Basel, Switzerland)*, 51(5), pp. 1–5. doi:10.1159/000524723.

Wang, S., Liu, H.-Y., Cheng, Y.-C. and Su, C.-H. (2021) ‘Exercise Dosage in Reducing the Risk of Dementia Development: Mode, Duration, and Intensity—A Narrative Review’, *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 18(24), p. 13331. doi:10.3390/ijerph182413331.

Weder, N.D., Aziz, R., Wilkins, K. and Tampi, R.R. (2007) ‘Frontotemporal Dementias: A Review’, *Annals of General Psychiatry*, 6(15), p. 15. doi:10.1186/1744-859X-6-15.

Weissgerber, T.L., Milic, N.M., Winham, S.J. and Garovic, V.D. (2015) ‘Beyond Bar and Line Graphs: Time for a New Data Presentation Paradigm’, *PLOS Biology*, 13(4), p. e1002128. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.1002128>.

Wolters, F.J., Chibnik, L.B., Waziry, R., Anderson, R., Berr, C., Beiser, A., Bis, J.C., Blacker, D., Bos, D., Brayne, C., Dartigues, J.-F., Darweesh, S.K.L., Davis-Plourde, K.L., de Wolf, F., Debette, S., Dufouil, C., Fornage, M., Goudsmit, J., Grasset, L. and Gudnason, V. (2020) ‘Twenty-seven-year time trends in dementia incidence in Europe and the United States’, *Neurology*, 95(5), pp. e519–e531. doi:10.1212/WNL.0000000000010022.

Wong, J.F.W., Kirk, A., Perlett, L., Karunanayake, C., Morgan, D. and O’Connell, M.E. (2020) ‘Characteristics of Young-Onset and Late-Onset Dementia Patients at a Remote Memory Clinic’, *The Canadian Journal of Neurological Sciences. Le Journal Canadien Des Sciences Neurologiques*, 47(3), pp. 320–327. doi:10.1017/cjn.2020.8.

Xiao, T., Wijnant, S.R.A., Licher, S., Terzikhan, N., Lahousse, L., Ikram, M.K., Brusselle, G.G. and Ikram, M.A. (2021) ‘Lung Function Impairment and the Risk of

Incident Dementia: The Rotterdam Study’, *Journal of Alzheimer’s Disease*, 82(2), pp. 621–630. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3233/jad-210162>.

Yang, S.-Y., Shan, C.-L., Qing, H., Wang, W., Zhu, Y., Yin, M.-M., Machado, S., Yuan, T.-F. and Wu, T. (2015) ‘The Effects of Aerobic Exercise on Cognitive Function of Alzheimer’s Disease Patients’, *CNS & neurological disorders drug targets*, 14(10), pp. 1292–7. doi:10.2174/1871527315666151111123319.

Yu, F., Vock, D.M., Zhang, L., Salisbury, D., Nelson, N.W., Chow, L.S., Smith, G., Barclay, T.R., Dysken, M. and Wyman, J.F. (2021) ‘Cognitive Effects of Aerobic Exercise in Alzheimer’s Disease: A Pilot Randomized Controlled Trial’, *Journal of Alzheimer’s Disease*, 80(1), pp. 233–244. doi:10.3233/jad-201100.

9. Appendices

1. NHS Letter of Ethical Approval

London - Riverside Research Ethics Committee

Ground Floor
Temple Quay House
2 The Square
Bristol
BS1 6PN

Telephone: 020 7104 8150

31 October 2022

Dr Lawrence Hayes
Lecturer
University of the West of Scotland
Technology Avenue
Glasgow
G72 0LH

Dear Dr Hayes

Study title: Functional capacity, physical activity, cardiac and vascular function, respiratory function, physical performance, muscular health, and mental wellbeing in people with young onset dementia
REC reference: 22/LO/0687
Protocol number: N/A
IRAS project ID: 316964

Thank you for your letter of 13 October 2022, responding to the Research Ethics Committee's (REC) request for further information on the above research and submitting revised documentation.

The further information has been considered on behalf of the Committee by the Chair.

Confirmation of ethical opinion

On behalf of the Committee, I am pleased to confirm a favourable ethical opinion for the above research on the basis described in the application form, protocol and supporting documentation as revised, subject to the conditions specified below.

Participant Information Sheet

Physical and psychological characterisation of young onset dementia

Firstly, thank you for taking time to visit the University of the West of Scotland. We are delighted for your help, and support with this project.

What is the purpose of the study?

We know that exercise has many benefits. However, it is unclear if people with young onset dementia may benefit more or less than people without young onset dementia.

We are asking people who have young onset dementia to take part in a research project consisting of several measurements of physical, cognitive, and physical performance. The aim of the project is to help us to characterise people with young onset dementia in terms of physical fitness, physical activity, and wellbeing and compare them to an age-matched cohort of people without young onset dementia. If there are deficits in particular parameters in people with young onset dementia, this will inform future studies of what outcomes may be improved with physical activity or exercise.

Will I be eligible for this study?

We are looking for participants aged 18 years and over who have been diagnosed with young onset dementia.

OR

have never had young onset dementia. i.e. 'control' participants.

Your participation is completely voluntary as no financial compensation is available (except travel expenses). You are free to withdraw from the study without having to provide a reason for doing so.

What are the benefits of taking part?

By participating in this research, you will be helping us understand the effects of young onset dementia. You will help us identify whether having young onset dementia influences physical fitness, physical activity, and wellbeing. This information may then be used by health professionals to help identify areas for improvement, and to help improve health.

What will be required of you, the participant?

Version 2 13/10/2022

If you decide to participate, you will be asked to visit University of the West of Scotland Lanarkshire Campus, Sports Science labs to participate in a battery of tests, including body composition (height and weight), ultrasound scans of the heart, arm, neck, and leg, lung function, cognitive function, cycling performance, grip strength, and dexterity. These tests will be carried out during your visit whereby travel expenses will be provided. Demonstration videos of the ultrasound scans, and physical capacity tests can be found [HERE](#).

Psychological tests (including assessments of anxiety and depression, fatigue, and quality of life) will be completed, but in your own time via a mobile app which we will guide you through use of.

What are the possible risks of taking part?

This study has been approved by the Integrated Research Application System (IRAS) which evaluates health, social and community care research in the UK, and therefore this project has been reviewed to contain minimal risks.

What happens if some of my results are abnormal?

If we detect an abnormality in your test results, Dr Munishankar, your Consultant psychiatrist, under whose care you are under, will write to you, and copy in your GP who can advise further investigations/assessments as necessary.

What if I decide I no longer wish to participate in the study?

If you decide you do not wish your data to be used, you have the right to withdraw the data at any point up to two weeks after participation. You do not have to provide a reason for withdrawing, and there will be no adverse consequences to you.

What should I do if I have a complaint to make about any aspect of the study?

If you are unhappy about any aspect of the study then you may either address this with the research team and/or Dr Lawrence Hayes, the principal investigator of the study. All contact details are provided at the end of this information sheet.

Will my taking part in this study be kept confidential?

All information that is provided will be confidential and will remain anonymous throughout the study via the use of participant number to identify you. All data will be stored on password protected computers available only to the research team.

It is planned that results from this study will be presented at conferences and published in peer-reviewed scientific journals. None of the results will be published on an individual basis and all results will be grouped, so results cannot be traced back to you personally.

After completion of the study, we will feedback to you with your individual results and the overall study results. You will, of course, be welcome to ask any questions or make comment on the results with the research team.

Thank you for your interest in this study and for taking the time to read this information sheet.

Contacts for further information:

Dr Lawrence Hayes
Principal Investigator
Sport and Physical Activity Research Institute
School of Health and Life Sciences
University of the West of Scotland
Glasgow, G72 0LH
E-mail [REDACTED]

3. Participant Letter of Invitation

Dear participant,

Re: Invitation to participate in a research project.

The purpose of this letter is to invite you to participate in a research study. The participant information sheet enclosed provides details of the purpose of the study, which you need to consider before deciding whether you would be willing to take part.

You are not obliged to take part in the study. If you do agree to participate, you are free to withdraw at any time without disadvantage to yourself about without needing to give a reason.

If you decide you wish to participate once you have considered the information provided, please get in contact via email (details at the end of this letter). Also, if you are unsure whether you wish to participate and just wish to find out more information you can get in contact, and it does not commit you to participating.

Many thanks for taking the time to read this information.

Yours sincerely,

Dr Lawrence Hayes

Principal Investigator

Sport and Physical Activity Research Institute

School of Health and Life Sciences

University of the West of Scotland

Glasgow, G72 0LH

E-mail: [REDACTED]

Version 1: 05/09/2022

4. Written Informed Consent

IRAS ID: 316964

Centre Number:

Study Number:

Participant Identification Number for this trial:

CONSENT FORM

Title of Project: **Physical and psychological characterisation of young onset dementia**
Name of Researcher: **Dr Lawrence Hayes**

Please initial box

1. I confirm that I have read the information sheet dated..... for the above study. I have had the opportunity to consider the Information, ask questions and have had these answered satisfactorily.

2. I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time without giving any reason, without my medical care or legal rights being affected.

3. I understand that the information collected about me will be used to support other research in the future and may be shared anonymously with other researchers.

4. I understand that the information held and maintained by the University of the West of Scotland may be used to help contact me or provide information about my health status.

5. I confirm that should an abnormal result be found, Dr Munishankar (part of the research team), Consultant psychiatrist, and patients all previously under her care, will write to me and copy in my GP and advise if further investigations or assessments as necessary.

6. I agree to take part in the above study.

When completed: 1 for participant; 1 for researcher site file; 1 to be kept in medical notes. VERSION 2 13/10/2022

Name of Participant

Date

Signature

Name of Person
seeking consent

Date

Signature

When completed: 1 for participant; 1 for researcher site file; 1 to be kept in medical notes. VERSION 2 13/10/2022

5. Physical Activity Readiness Questionnaire (PAR-Q)

Physical Activity Readiness Questionnaire (PAR-Q)

Name:

Date of Birth:

Address:

Nationality:

Post Code:

Email:

Telephone:

Emergency Contact Name:

Emergency Contact No:

Your health & safety is very important to us. Many health benefits are associated with regular exercise and the completion of a Par-Q is a sensible first step to take if you plan to increase the amount of physical activity in your life.

PART 1 – Please click to place an X in the relevant answers below (Yes / No)	<u>YES</u>	<u>NO</u>
1. Has your doctor ever said that you have a heart condition and that you should only do physical activity recommended by a doctor?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. Do you feel pain in your chest when you do physical activity?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. In the past month, have you had chest pain when you were not doing physical activity?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4. Do you lose your balance because of dizziness, or do you ever lose consciousness?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5. Do you have a bone or joint problem (for example, back, knee or hip) that could be made worse by a change in your physical activity?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6. Is your doctor currently prescribing drugs (for example, water pills) for your blood pressure or heart condition?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
7. Do you know of any other reason why you should not do physical activity?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

PART 2

If you've answered 'YES' to any of the above questions please give full details here:

The University Of The West of Scotland assume no liability for persons who undertake physical activity, and if in doubt after completing this questionnaire, consult your doctor prior to physical activity.

Please notify us if any of the above information should ever change.

Signed:

Date:

6. Title and Examiner Approval Form

POSTGRADUATE RESEARCH DEGREE THESIS TITLE AND EXAMINERS APPROVAL (TEA) FORM

IMPORTANT NOTE: Complete as instructed and Lead Supervisor (LS) to submit this document electronically for C-DCB approval. Candidate should also attach the hard copy of the submitted document with the bound thesis.

COMPLETE AND SIGN 8 WEEKS TO SUBMISSION

PART 1a: CANDIDATE AND THESIS – Completed by Candidate

Candidate's name	Ethan Berry		Banner ID	b00343919	
School	Health and Life Sciences	Campus	Lanarkshire	Degree	MRes
Lead Supervisor's name	Dr Lawrence Hayes		Expected submission date	23/01/2024	
Provide an accurate title of the thesis to be submitted – proposed title (Sentence case only).					
Title of thesis	Physiological and psychological characterisation of young onset dementia: A case control study				

PART 1b: CANDIDATE AND LEAD SUPERVISOR CONFIRMATION – Completed by Student and Lead Supervisor

Candidate signature⁽ⁱ⁾	[Redacted]	Date	15/09/2023
Lead Supervisor signature	[Redacted]	Date	15/09/2023

(i) I confirm that I have consulted my Lead Supervisor about the intended submission and that: (1) I have provided accurate and complete information, (2) I have obtained any required ethical approval for my research and (3) I understand the University does not guarantee that the degree will be granted in time for attendance at the next Graduation Ceremony.

LEAD SUPERVISOR RECOMMENDS EXAMINERS WITHIN 5-8 WEEKS TO SUBMISSION

PART 2a: Internal Examiners (at least one examiner to have previous relevant examination experience)

Internal Examiner 1	Title/Position	Dr / Lecturer	Name	Mia Burleigh	
School	Health and Life Sciences		Previous UK Postgraduate Research Degree examination experience?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No
Internal Examiner 2⁽ⁱⁱ⁾	Title/Position	Dr/ Lecturer	Name	Rachel Kimble	
School	Health and Life Sciences		Previous UK Postgraduate Research Degree examination experience?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No

(ii) Internal Examiner 2 with no UK Postgraduate Research Degree examination experience to be accompanied by an experienced Internal Examiner 1.

PART 2b: External Examiners (Please note that external examiner CVs must be attached)

External Examiner 1	Title/Position	Dr / Senior Lecturer	Name	Christopher Gaffney	
Postal address	Health Innovation Campus, Lancaster Medical School, Lancaster University, LA1 4YW		Eligible to work in the UK?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No
Email address	[Redacted]		Previous UK Postgraduate Research Degree examination experience?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No
External Examiner 2⁽ⁱⁱⁱ⁾	Title/Position		Name		
Postal address			Eligible to work in the UK?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No
Email address			Previous UK Postgraduate Research Degree examination experience?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No

(iii) Two external examiners are required for candidates who are full-time academic staff of the University of the West of Scotland.

PART 2c: SCHOOL AUTHORISATION – Parts 2a - 2c to be completed by Lead Supervisor and authorised by relevant Schools

I confirm correctness and completeness of the above information and authorise the examination arrangements.			
PGR Coordinator (Name)	Laura Carey	School	Health and Life Sciences

POSTGRADUATE RESEARCH DEGREE THESIS TITLE AND EXAMINERS APPROVAL (TEA) FORM

AUTHORISE NO LESS THAN 4 WEEKS TO SUBMISSION

Dean 1 or nominee (Name)	Beverley Young	Candidate's School	Health and Life Sciences
Dean 2 or nominee (Name)^(iv)	(if different)	Internal Examiner's School	Health and Life Sciences (if different)
PGR Coordinator (Signature)		Dean 1 or nominee (signature)	
Schools authorisation date(s) (completed by PGR Coordinator)	15/09/2023	Dean 2 or nominee (signature)	

(iv) If different, authorisations to be obtained from Dean or nominee of the Internal Examiner's School as well as Candidate's School Dean.

PART 3: LEAD SUPERVISOR SUBMITS FOR FINAL APPROVAL BY CHAIR OF DOCTORAL COLLEGE BOARD (C-DCB)

C-DCB Name	Professor Milan Radosavljevic	Signature		Date:	26/09/2023
-------------------	-------------------------------	------------------	--	--------------	------------

INSTRUCTIONS: Lead Supervisor to submit completed and signed form to PGR Coordinator for school authorisation before submitting a scan of the authorised hard copy (PDF or JPEG) for final DCB approval to pgr@uws.ac.uk.